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Detection of SARS Cov-2 IgG, and IgA Antibodies in Patient's Serum, Saliva and Nasal fluid using ELISA

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By

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بِسْمِ اللّٰهِ الرَّحْمٰنِ الرَّحِیْمِ

﴿وَلَقَدْ آتَيْنَا دَاوُودَ وَسُلَيْمَانَ عِلْمًا وَقَالَا

الْحَمْدُ لِلّٰهِ الَّذِي فَضَّلَنَا عَلَى كَثِيرٍ مِّنْ عِبَادِهِ

الْمُؤْمِنِينَ﴾

صدق الله العظيم

(سورة النمل الآية 15)

In the name of God, the Merciful, the Compassionate

﴿And We had certainly given to David and Solomon knowledge, and they said, "Praise [is due] to Allah, who has favored us over many of His believing servants ﴾

Allah Almighty is Truthful

(Al-Namel, phrase 15)

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Abstract

Method:

For the purpose of detecting SARS-CoV-2 IgA-RBD and IgG-NCP, a set of a randomized three patients' groups (a total 55 subjects, randomized into 20 Non previously infected control, 20 fully vaccinated people from Al Salam teaching hospital vaccination ward upon receiving the vaccine doses, and 15 patients newly recovered from SARS-CoV-2 infection from Al Shifaa quarantine hospital after remission from COVID-19 infection and preparing to discharge). The collection was made as three fluid samples; serum, saliva, and nasal fluid, for a total of three samples per patient, to make a total of 165 samples to be tested. By using a commercial immunoassay kit (Anti-SARS-CoV-2 ELISA RBD IgA, and Anti-SARS-CoV-2 NCP ELISA IgG) the study was designed to assess the levels of the immunoglobulin in each sample from different health status and anatomical locations to give the statistical difference and the correct conclusion regarding this study. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 24, and Microsoft Excel version (16.0.15028). Test equations were performed via Mann-Whitney U Test and the Kruskal-Wallis H test. To evaluate the non-gaussian distribution among the study groups for each of the outcomes, $p < 0.05$ was undertaken as statistically significant.

Results:

The results showed that two doses of mRNA BNT162b2 vaccine Comirnaty (Pfizer/BioNTech, New York, NY, USA), elicited a powerful anti-SARS-CoV-2 nasal and salivary IgA and IgG monoclonal antibody protection (as compared to control 0.625 Cut of Index (COI). The vaccinated subjects resulted in a higher median salivary concentration of IgG against Nucleocapsid protein (NCP) values as

1.69 COI, with a p-value of 0.0001. Similar results for the median salivary concentration of the vaccinated subjects in IgA against receptor binding domain (RBD) with a value of 2.41 COI, if compared to control median values of 0.67 COI, with a p-value of 0.0001); (as compared to control 0.34 COI, the vaccinated subjects resulted in a higher median nasal concentration of IgG NCP values as 1.52 COI, with a p-value of 0.0001. Similar results for the median nasal concentration of IgA RBD with a value of 1.84 COI, if compared to control median values of 0.71 COI). Two injections 25 days apart shown to trigger a stronger titer of protective immunity as compared to a single early shot, still it's less robust compared to the titers measured for the recovered subjects from COVID-19 infection. The vaccinated subjects are significantly better tested via IgA in Saliva as compared to IgG, because of the higher median values for the IgA vs IgG, 2.41 COI and 1.69 COI respectively with a p-value of 0.008. In a similar state, the IgA is the best test for the convalescent subjects in term of nasal fluid samples investigations, as the median value is comparatively higher than the median value of IgG, 1.94 COI and 1.47 COI respectively, with a p-value of 0.045.

Conclusion:

Take into consideration that there was a lack of trustable ELISA based assays with specially designed kit for this purpose, focusing on nasal and salivary secretions, the current study proofed that our pre investigational and investigational data are consistent. The results of this study indicate, that a protective antigen specific nasal and salivary monoclonal antibody, can be triggered following proper vaccination regimen with mRNA COVID-19 vaccine, so this paves the way for using mucosal protective antibodies detection kits, as a suitable alternative option as a less invasive method compared to serum investigations, for detecting the protection against SARS-CoV-2 infection, induced by vaccine.

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List of abbreviations

3CL	3C-Like Protease
AIM2	Interferon-Inducible Protein 2
BALT	Bronchus-Associated Lymphoid Tissue
Bi-pap	Bilevel Positive Airway Pressure
cGAS	Cyclic GMP–AMP Synthase
COI	Cutoff Index Value
CRISPR/Cas9	Clustered Regularly Interspaced Short Palindromic Repeats / CRISPR-Associated Protein 9
CRO	Crotonaldehyde
CXCL-10	Cysteine-X (Any Amino Acid)-Cysteine Motif Chemokine Ligand 10
DAMPs	Damage-Associated Molecular Patterns
ENaC- α	Epithelial Sodium Channel A
EUL	Emergency Use Listing Procedure
GMP-AMP	Guanosine Monophosphate – Adenosine Monophosphate
GRL-0617	5-Amino-2-Methyl-N-[(1R)-1-Naphthalen-1-Ylethyl] Benzamide 0617
GSDM-D	Gasdermin D
HIV	Human Immunodeficiency Virus
I.M.	Intramuscular
I.N.	Intranasal
ICU	Intensive Care Units
IFNs	Interferons
IFN γ	Interferon-Gamma
IgE	Immunoglobulin E
IHD	Ischemic Heart Disease
IKK	Ikappab Kinase
IL-10	Interleukin 10
IL-13	Interleukin 13
IL-5	Interleukin 5
ILCs	Innate Lymphoid Cells
IRF3	Interferon Regulatory Factor 3
ISGs	Interferon-Stimulated Genes
ISRE	Interferon-Sensitive Response Element

IVA	Influenza Virus Of Type A
JAKSTAT	Anus Kinases and Signal Transducer and Activator Of Transcription Proteins
LGP2	Laboratory Of Genetics and Physiology 2
LRT	Lower Respiratory Tract
MAPKs	Mitogen Activated Protein Kinases
MAVS	Mitochondrial Antiviral-Signaling Protein
MBL	Mannose-Binding Lectin
MCP-1	Monocyte Chemoattractant Protein-1
MDA5	Melanoma Differentiation-Associated Protein 5
MIP-1	Macrophage Inflammatory Proteins-1
MIS-C	Multisystem Inflammatory Syndrome In Children
MyD88	Myeloid Differentiation Primary Response 88
NAAT	Nucleic Acid Amplification Test
NaCl	Sodium Chloride
NALT	Nasal Lymphoid Tissue
NK	Natural Killer Cells
NLR	Nucleotide-Binding Domain Leucine-Rich Repeat
NLRP3	Nod-Like Receptor Family Pyrin Domain Containing 3
NSP3	Multi-Domain Non-Structural Protein 3
NTD	N-Terminal Domain
A°	Absorbance
ORF3b	Open Reading Frame 3b
PAMPs	Pathogen-Associated Molecular Pattern Molecules
PANoptosis	Pyroptosis, Apoptosis, And Necroptosis
PC-controlled	Pc Controlled
PCs	Plasma Cells
PD-1	Programmed Cell Death Protein 1
pIgA	Polymeric Immunoglobulin A
PLpro	Papain-Like Protease
PP tube	Polypropylene Tube
PRR	Pathogen Recognition Receptors

PSO	Post-Symptom Onset
RCU	Respiratory Care Unit
RDs	Respiratory Distress Syndrome
RIG-I	Retinoic Acid-Inducible Gene I
RLR	Retinoic Acid-Inducible Gene-I-Like Receptors
RRR	Relative Risk Reduction
RT-qPCR	Reverse Transcription Quantitative Real-Time Polymerase Chain Reaction
SARSS366	Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome S366 Protein
SIR	Second/Sequential Immune Responses
SPSS	Statistical Package for The Social Sciences
SST tube	Serum Separator Tube
STAT 1	Signal Transducer and Activator of Transcription 1
STING	Stimulator Of Interferon Genes
TBK	TANK Binding Kinase
Tfh	T Follicular Helper Cells
TIGIT	Thymus Cell Immunoglobulin and Immunoreceptor Tyrosine-Based Inhibitory Motif Domain
TIM-3	Thymus Cell Immunoglobulin Mucin-3
TLR	Toll-Like Receptors
TMB/H2O2	Tetramethylbenzidine/Hydrogen Peroxide
TRAF	Tumor Necrosis Factor Receptor-Associated Factor
TRIF	Adapter-Inducing Interferon-B
URT	Upper Respiratory Tract
WHO	The World Health Organization

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Introduction

1.1-a. The Linked Serological Assay Studies.

The mucosal humoral immunity has a central role in the opposition fight against SARS-COV-2 infections (COVID-19), (Wang et al., 2021, Lapuente *et al.*, 2021, Azzi *et al.*, 2022). Building on the established data regarding SARS-COV-2 infections, the virus initiates multiplication and infection by colonizing the upper respiratory tract, in this anatomical site, the secretory protective immunoglobulins give strong defense against initiation of this viral colonization, imparting natural immune protection to the host upper mucosa of the host respiratory tract (Matuchansky C. 2021).

Protective monoclonal antibodies can be triggered and became detectable in the upper respiratory mucosa following exposure to the virus, making the mucosal barrier the first line of natural defense against the viral colonizing infection (Smith *et al.*, 2021). The key player in the mucosal immunity is the S-IgA (secretory IgA), which is the main antibody of mucosal protection. It plays crucial rule in neutralizing invasive pathogens invading the mucosa of the upper respiratory tract, especially viruses, imparting a protective effect on the local mucosal area from viral colonizing infection (Vâță *et al.*, 2022).

Disastrous immune response against the virus in the lung will result in a broad spectrum of symptoms and presentations, ranging from the

asymptomatic state to a critical illness in the form of (ADRS), (Klenerman, 2020). Mild respiratory symptoms may develop in some subjects, being in the form of (ageusia, headache, low grade fever, loss of smell, congestion or runny nose), without progressing to severe respiratory symptoms (El-Anwar *et al.*, 2021). This in part can be explained to the fact that mucosal immunity, namely Monoclonal antibody S-IgA will neutralize SARS-COV-2 particles, prevent them from reaching the distal respiratory epithelial mucosal cells and initiate severe infection, this reflects the protective immune barrier rule of mucosal immunoglobulins in the protection against COVID-19 infection (Lapuente *et al.*, 2021).

According to previous studies, protective antibodies in the oral cavity and respiratory mucosa can be of special importance in prevention and protection against SARS-COV-2 like respiratory viruses, especially Influenza virus, and respiratory syncytial virus (RSV), as well as non-respiratory viruses, Hepatitis C virus being among the most important of these viruses (Bagga *et al.*, 2015, Vâță *et al.*, 2022). During the early time of COVID-19 outbreak most of the focus was given to the humoral neutralizing virus specific IgG and IgM, to assess the fighting capacity of the body against COVID-19 (Guo *et al.*, 2020, Van Caesele *et al.*, 2020, Shah *et al.*, 2021, Khoshkam *et al.*, 2021, Vâță *et al.*, 2022). Earlier studies focused on the fact that within the first week post symptoms onset, IgA more than IgG and IgM is likely to be more potent at blocking and neutralizing the systemic spread of SARS-COV-2, still the clinical effectiveness is more related to the access of these antibodies to the mucosal surfaces in the site of viral entry, to be considered effective at blocking the viral initiation of infection (Matuchansky C. 2021, Lapuente *et al.*, 2021).

In the mucosal area Secretory IgA (S-IgA), the main type of antibodies there is made by the resident plasma cells as a dimeric molecule of IgA. IgG is also present to some extent on these mucosal surfaces, passively leaking from the blood circulation. It appears to be derived from the oral gingival crevicular epithelium, even though some may be produced by local immune cells in the mucosa (Ibiang *et al.*, 2022). Previous studies have proven that patients with Severe Acute SARS-COV-2 infections will develop a high titer of neutralizing specific S-IgA immunoglobulins in the salivary secretions (Aita *et al.*, 2020, He *et al.*, 2020, Pisanic *et al.*, 2020b, Varadhachary *et al.*, 2020, Azzi *et al.*, 2022, Thompson *et al.*, 2022). SARS-COV-2 Viral particle tie up, fusion, and ingress to the interior of the target cell is critically mediated by the SARS-COV-2 spike (S) protein on the surface of viral particle (Xia *et al.*, 2020, Yu *et al.*, 2021, Zhang *et al.*, 2021). This S protein is made up of two individual parts, S1 and S2. S1 protein fraction mediates attachment to the infected cell surface elements (Angiotensin Converting Enzyme 2 receptor ACE-2), via its specific receptor binding domain RBD (Smith *et al.*, 2021). Cell membrane fusion components are located on the S2 fraction of this spike protein (Jaimes *et al.*, 2020, Zhang *et al.*, 2021).

Upon initiation of infection, SARS-COV-2 attaches to host cell membrane elements and receptors via its S1-RBD domain interaction, such interaction would trigger three dimensional changes in the S2 domain, subsequently fusion and ingress of viral particle into the host cell (Jaimes *et al.*, 2020, Zhang *et al.*, 2021). Spread of SARS-COV-2 particles between individuals occurs first in the upper respiratory tract of the infected individual, the reason is that ACE 2 receptors are physiologically highly expressed in this anatomical location (Khoshkam *et al.*, 2021). Receptor Binding Domain

(RBD), is considered the most antigenic of SARS-COV-2 proteins capable of triggering a powerful neutralizing antibody (Martínez *et al.*, 2022).

During the time of pandemic outbreak, assay of SARS-COV-2 neutralizing antibodies was considered crucial for diagnosis and follow up of patients with COVID-19 infection, as it gives a meaningful data regarding the immunity condition of the subjects (Shah *et al.*, 2021, Duesberg *et al.*, 2022, Infantino *et al.*, 2022). Serological test kits designed to investigate the immunogenicity, targets the anti-SARS-COV-2 circulating anti-spike antibodies, including IgG, Targeting full Spike (S), its subdomain (S1), or the (RBD) domain (Horn *et al.*, 2022). Powerful neutralizing antibodies in the serum like IgG, as a protective immunoglobulin response against the SARS-COV-2 RBD domain of the S1 spike protein subdomain, is triggered by the SARS-COV-2 mRNA vaccine, BNT162b2 Comirnaty (Pfizer/BioNTech, New York, NY, USA) and Spikevax (Moderna, Cambridge, MA, USA), (Barda *et al.*, 2021, Zhang *et al.*, 2021). Whether the vaccines have the ability to trigger mucosal immune response, or whether the vaccine against COVID-19 triggered a robust humoral immunity is mostly unexpected (Barda *et al.*, 2021). In the scope of vaccination worldwide, the applicability of a highly robust antibody assay, to be considered a cost effective less invasive method was a target goal to be achieved to track community health immunity and measure the extent of success of vaccination strategy globally (Cristiano *et al.*, 2021, Šošić *et al.*, 2021, Makhoul *et al.*, 2022). Based on the discussion, a reliable quantitative and neutralizing assay against SARS-COV-2 are crucial to follow up immune response to the vaccine, and such tests appear mandatory, if a link can be established between the antibody titers and future shielding against reinfection was made possible (Infantino *et al.*, 2022).

In recent studies, injecting a vaccine designed in the form of vectored Adenovirus encodes for spike protein, show that it encodes and elicits a strong IgA and neutralizing immunoglobulins, this would effectively block SARS-CoV-2 viral spread in the lower and even upper respiratory tract (Li *et al.*, 2021, Văță *et al.*, 2022b). Linking to the above text, saliva and nasal derived immunoglobulins would be of some relevance to reflect mRNA vaccines efficacy at preventing nasal and oral SARS-COV-2 infection and dissipation (Varadhachary *et al.*, 2020). The extent to which the host immunological response and protection, can be reflected by the titer of anti-spike specific IgA and IgG immunoglobulins, in the oropharyngeal and lower respiratory mucosa (Smith *et al.*, 2021). Even though, currently, in order to define a reliable analytical and standardized assessment method, to detect mucosal reactivity to COVID-19 vaccination.

Accordingly in order to differentiate the vaccine from the naturally acquired mucosal and systemic antibody responses, this study was designed to detect anti-SARS-CoV-2 IgG-NCP and IgA-RBD in the study population. All of the three groups, namely (Vaccinated individuals, healthy individuals as control, and COVID-19 individuals) on three different fluid specimens from these patients, saliva, serum, and nasal samples, utilize a commercially available (Enzyme Linked Immunosorbent Assay) ELISA kits.

1.1-b. Comparative Vaccine Efficacy versus Placebo,

Since the World Health Organization classified the Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) a pandemic on March 11, 2020 (WHO Director-General's Opening Remarks at the Media Briefing on COVID-19 - 11 March 2020, 2020), it has afflicted tens of millions of people worldwide (COVID-19 Map - Johns Hopkins Coronavirus Resource Center, n.d.). The most vulnerable groups to COVID-19 and its consequences include older individuals, those with certain comorbid diseases, and front-line professionals. According to the findings, younger individuals and other groups become more and more infected with COVID-19 and SARS-CoV-2, respectively (CDC, 2020). To bring the epidemic under control, which has had catastrophic effects on health, the economy and society, a preventive vaccination that are safe and effective are urgently required.

Clinical trials of the vaccine candidate BNT162b2 (Chen *et al.*, 2022), a lipid nanoparticle formulation (Kauffman *et al.*, 2016, Karikó, 2021), nucleoside-modified RNA (modRNA), encoding the SARS-CoV-2 full-length spike, modified by two proline mutations to lock it in the prefusion conformation, a phase 1 safety and immunogenicity results have already been presented (Wrapp *et al.*, 2020).

Two 30 μ g doses of BNT162b2 produced strong antigen-specific CD8⁺ and Th1-type CD4⁺ T-cell responses as well as significant SARS-CoV-2 neutralizing antibody titers in tests performed in the United States and Germany among healthy men and women (Guerrera *et al.*, 2021). Despite older people having a weaker neutralizing response than younger adults, 30 μ g of BNT162b2 induced 50% neutralizing geometric mean titers in both older and younger individuals that were higher than the geometric mean titer

seen in a human convalescent serum panel. Additionally, the short-term local (i.e., injection site) and systemic reactions were mostly reflected by the reactogenicity profile of BNT162b2. The development of the BNT162b2 vaccine candidate into phase 3 was encouraged by these results.

The safety, immunogenicity, and effectiveness of 30 µg of BNT162b2 in preventing COVID-19 in people aged 16 and older, were concluded in this study. A collection of data on the immunogenicity of vaccines and the longevity of the immune response to vaccination are still being collected, thus such data are probably supportive in this respect.

1.2 Aims of the study

This study aims to:

I – Investigate the efficacy of ELISA based technique designed to cover serum samples, to detect SARS CoV-2 specific antibodies (IgG, and IgA), in Saliva, Nasal fluid and serum.

II – Compare the diagnostic value from approaching either saliva or nasal fluid as alternative to serum, in detecting SARS CoV-2 infection status and vaccination status based on triggered antibody response.

III – Check the potential prognostic value of sequential salivary sampling in predicting future attacks, based on linked antibodies titer studies, as well as monitoring long term vaccine efficacy.

IV – Help to make decision, of whether choosing saliva as alternative to serum, to be a potential consistent noninvasive sampling site, for either checking and/or following up immune response to either SARS CoV-2 infection or vaccination.

V – Give easy access method for checking and following up immune response to SARS-CoV-2 vaccination status, via salivary testing only instead of serum sampling.

Chapter two

Literatures Review

2.1 Understanding SARS-CoV-2 virus and COVID-19 infection

2.1.a – Origins

There has been a great deal of interest in figuring out how Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) initially appeared in the human population since the first reports of a new severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS)-like coronavirus in December 2019 in Wuhan, China. Although COVID-19's first case was officially discovered in early December of 2019 SARS-CoV-2 most likely spread to people much earlier. Significant variations in hospital and search engine traffic were observed in Wuhan from August to October 2019 by pointing to a potential earlier occurrence of COVID-19. According to a recent joint WHO-China investigation on the origins of SARS-CoV-2, the most recent ancestor is most likely to have lived between mid-November and early December, with a range of late September to early December. the findings are consistent with the available data and indicate that the first COVID-19 case likely occurred between early October and mid-November. Furthermore, based on the letratures, the first cases are most likely to occur on November 17, 2019. (Huang *et al.*, 2020, Nsoesie, 2020, and Publications Detail, n.d., “WHO-convened Global Study of Origins of SARS-CoV-2: China Part,” 2021).

2.1-b Transmission

The main method of transmission for the Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) is direct person-to-person respiratory

contact. Virus released in the respiratory secretions when an infected person coughs, sneezes, or talks can infect another person if it is inhaled or comes into contact with the mucous membranes. It is believed to spread primarily through close contact (i.e., within six feet or two meters) via respiratory particles. Although contaminated surfaces are not regarded to be a primary route of transmission, infection may still happen if a person touches his eyes, nose, or mouth after having his hands contaminated by these fluids or after touching contaminated surfaces. The possibility of longer distance airborne transmission in confined, inadequately ventilated settings has been emphasized by sporadic reports of SARS-CoV-2 outbreaks (such as at a restaurant or on a bus). (Shen *et al.*, 2020, Duval *et al.*, 2022, Meyerowitz *et al.*, 2021).

The risk of SARS-CoV-2 transmission increases in the first 7 to 10 days after infection and peaks in the early stages of sickness. Thereafter, the risk of transmission diminishes. After 10 days of sickness, transmission is rare. It is anticipated that infectiousness peaked between two days before and one day after symptom onset and reduced within seven days.

It has been widely established that SARS-CoV-2 may spread from people who are infected but have no symptoms to others who subsequently develop symptoms and are thus called presymptomatic. A study of a SARS-CoV-2 epidemic in a long-term care facility provides evidence for the biological foundation for this; infectious virus was grown from upper respiratory tract specimens from presymptomatic and asymptomatic patients as early as six days before the onset of characteristic symptoms. Asymptomatic individuals' upper respiratory tract viral RNA levels and persistence are comparable to those of symptomatic patient. Asymptomatic people tend to have a lower transmission risk than those who are symptomatic. According to CDC modeling research, 59 % of transmission might be

ascribed to those who are asymptomatic, with 24 % coming from people who continue to be asymptomatic and 35 percent from people who are presymptomatic (Bai *et al.*, 2020, Böhmer *et al.*, 2020, Johansson *et al.*, 2021, Li *et al.*, 2021).

2.1.c – Taxonomy

The International Committee on Taxonomy of Viruses (ICTV), which regulates viral taxonomy, set realm as the highest taxonomic rank for viruses (Current ICTV Taxonomy Release | ICTV, n.d.). There are six identified viral realms, which are connected by certain, highly conserved traits:

- Adnaviria, which includes Archaeal filamentous viruses with double-stranded DNA (dsDNA) genomes of the A-form that encode a particular alpha-helical major capsid protein;
- Duplodnaviria, which includes all dsDNA viruses that encode the HK97-fold major capsid protein;
- Monodnaviria, which includes all single-stranded DNA (ssDNA) viruses that code for an endonuclease from the HUH superfamily and their offspring;
- Riboviria, which includes all RNA viruses that code for reverse transcriptase and RNA-dependent RNA polymerase;
- Ribozyviria, which includes hepatitis delta-like viruses with circular, negative-sense ssRNA genomes;
- Varidnaviria, which includes all dsDNA viruses that code for a vertical jelly roll major capsid protein.

The viral nomenclature and criteria for virus categorization are created by the (ICTV) system. With the development of molecular technology over the last several years, including next-generation sequencing, viruses are now categorized according to their evolutionary and ancestral ties, with the use of methods like phylogenetic and

genomic features as the foundation. The Committee's guidelines for naming provide those viruses must be categorized in a hierarchical manner, with the present classification system consisting of fifteen levels (Figure 2.1). Due to the new coronavirus's genetic resemblance to the 2003 SARS virus, it was first known as 2019-nCoV before being dubbed SARS-CoV-2. SARS-CoV-2 is a single-stranded positive-sense RNA virus that is a member of the order Nidovirales and the subfamily Orthocoronavirinae of the family Coronaviridae. α -coronavirus, β -coronavirus, γ -coronavirus, and delta-coronaviruses are members of the Orthocoronavirinae subfamily. The new coronavirus is a β -coronavirus (Figure 2.2). The sickness brought on by SARS-CoV-2 was given the term COVID-19 (coronavirus disease 2019) by the World Health Organization (WHO), which is in charge of designating human diseases. (Naming the Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19) and the Virus That Causes It, n.d., Rehman *et al.*, 2020, Gorbalenya *et al.*, 2020). The Nidovirales order, which comprises the virus families Coronaviridae, Arteriviridae, Mesoniviridae, and Roniviridae, is dominated by coronaviruses. A subfamily of the viral family Coronaviridae is referred to as the Coronavirinae, which includes coronaviruses (with the other being the Torovirinae subfamily). The

Figure 2.1: Fifteen-degree classification hierarchy of viruses and classification of the newly emerged SARS-CoV-2 virus in this taxonomic hierarchy.

Note: adapted from (Safarzadeh *et al.*, 2021)

four genera of coronavirinae viruses are further broken down. These include the coronaviruses alpha, beta, gamma, and delta. As was already noted, the beta coronavirus genus includes the SARS-CoV-2 virus, (Figure 2.1, Figure 2.2).

Figure 2.2: Classification of Coronaviruses

Note: adapted from (Rehman *et al.*, 2020)

Although furin cleavage sites facilitate the hydrolysis of glycoproteins in plasma membranes necessary for MERS-CoV or SARS-CoV-2 to enter cells and infect people, knowledge regarding coronaviruses (CoVs) containing these sites is exceedingly restricted. The worldwide epidemiology and evolutionary history of SARS-CoV-2 and 248 additional CoVs with 86 diverse furin cleavage sites that have been identified in 24 animal hosts in 28 countries since 1954 have therefore been studied. Two of the five CoVs known to infect humans (HCoV-OC43 and HCoV-HKU1) also include furin cleavage sites in addition to MERS-CoV and SARS-CoV-2. Additionally, human enteric coronavirus (HECV-4408) has been identified in humans (first in Germany in 1988) and is thought to have spread from bovine origins due to spillover occurrences. This virus possesses a furin cleavage site. Finally, the polytropic character of SARS-CoV-2 and SARS-CoV-2-like CoVs may be explained by the existence of furin cleavage sites, which would be useful for containing the COVID-19 pandemic and preventing the development of new CoVs, (X. Liu *et al.*, 2021), as in (Figure 2.3).

Figure 2.3: Phylogenetic relationships of coronavirus spike proteins with furin cleavage sites. The branches are colored according to virus genus (purple = Alpha-CoV, yellow = Beta-CoV, light blue = Gamma-CoV). Animal shapes indicate the viruses' main hosts and are colored according to the genus of virus they host. The leaves show the virus species, GenBank Accession numbers, and furin cleavage site motifs. Four coronaviruses with furin cleavage sites known to infect humans (HCoV-OC43, HCoV-HKU1, MERS-CoV, and SARS-CoV) and a human enteric coronavirus 4408 (HECV-4408) first detected in Germany in 1988 are marked in red. The first recorded coronavirus with a furin cleavage site was detected in Gallus and is marked in blue.

Note: adapted from (X. Liu et al., 2021)

2.1.d - Viral Life Cycle and Host Cell Invasion

The five stages of a virus's life cycle with a host are attachment, penetration, biosynthesis, maturity, and release. Viruses enter host cells by endocytosis or membrane fusion after attaching to host receptors (penetration). Viral RNA reaches the nucleus of the host cells once the viral components have been released within. Viral proteins are produced using viral mRNA (biosynthesis). Then, after maturing, additional virus particles are produced and discharged (V'kovski *et al.*, 2021). An overview of the viral life cycle is shown in (figure 2.4).

Figure 2.4: SARS-CoV-2 viral life cycle.

Note: from (V'kovski *et al.*, 2020)

Infected Tissue and Cell Types

The spike protein is a key target for neutralizing antibodies produced after infection and is a component of both mRNA and adenovirus-based vaccines. It also enables the virus' attachment to host cell-surface receptors and fusion with cell membranes. Given the ongoing creation of new lineages of new variations, these are active topics of study. A study of cell lines from mice, bats, non-human primates, and humans revealed that different cell types were vulnerable to the virus. These included the lungs, intestines, liver, kidneys, and nervous system, with cell lines that express the hACE-2 receptor (hACE-2) often having a higher viral load. This study shows that SARS-CoV-2 can infect a wide range of cell types and that hACE-2 serves as a crucial entry route, despite the fact that cell lines do not represent physiological circumstances. The virus may infect cells of the epithelial, vascular endothelial, pancreatic, and mucosal types ACE2 receptor expression was shown to be predominantly localized to lung pneumocytes, stomach. (Song *et al.*, 2018, Letko *et al.*, 2020, Ali & Vijayan, 2020, Chu *et al.*, 2020, Puelles *et al.*, 2020, Yan *et al.*, 2021.), absorptive enterocytes, and nasal mucosa goblet secretory cells by single-cell RNA sequencing (scRNA- seq). The systemic variety and extent of SARS-effects CoV-2's are often explained in part by the location of ACE2 receptors. Multiple organs, including the lungs, pharynx, liver, nasal mucosa, trachea, intestines, skin, pancreas, kidney, brain, and heart, are infected by SARS-CoV-2, according to human postmortem investigations. The respiratory tract had the greatest amounts of SARS-CoV-2 copies per cell, as determined by in situ hybridization and indirect immunofluorescence, whereas the kidneys, liver, heart, and brain had the lowest levels, according to a study of 27 patients .These studies suggest that the virus expresses itself differently in each organ, which may be influenced by the concentrations of the ACE2-receptor and associated entry factors (cluster of differentiation 4 [CD4], transmembrane protease, serine-2 [TMPRSS2], transferrin

receptor protein 1 [TRFC1], and neuropilin-1 [NRP1]) in each type of organ (Puelles *et al.*, 2020, and Park *et al.*, 2022).

2.1.e – Pathogenicity

The pathogenicity of SARS-CoV-2 occurs through the following mechanisms:

1- A unique furin cleavage site in SARS-CoV-2

The Coronaviruses responsible for earlier pandemics have structural similarities with SARS-CoV-2, more notably with SARS-CoV-1, with which it has a tight genomic homology (79.5%) and protein homology (95-100%). Additionally, it shared ACE2, the primary host cell entrance receptor, with SARS-CoV-1. However, it is unique from SARS-CoV-1 or other SARS-related viruses due to the insertion of a furin-cleavage site (FCS) containing multi-basic amino-acids (PRRAR) at the S1/S2 junction of the viral spike protein (S). FCS is considered to be an evolutionary gain in SARS-CoV-2 and is hypothesized to be a crucial element for its high infectivity and transmissibility despite being present in a number of other CoV family members, including MERS-CoV, HKU1-CoV, and OC43-CoV. Although several other proteases, such as TMPRSS2 and cathepsin-B or L (CTS-B or L), may effectively cleave the S1/S2 site of SARS-CoV-2 S, the insertion of FCS may have given SARS-CoV-2 certain advantages. This possibility has to be further investigated. (Naqvi *et al.*, 2020, Xu *et al.*, 2020, Coutard *et al.*, 2020, Johnson *et al.*, 2020, Jaimes *et al.*, 2020).

2- SARS-CoV-2 manipulates host immune response

The host immune responses are the principal target of SARS-CoV-2 specific virulence factors. Of particular, severe COVID-19 patients often have an overactive innate immune response characterized by a "cytokine storm". According to recent research, a virus may fool the host immune system by triggering a delayed but hyperactive innate immune response that produces a cytokine storm and, in turn, can

suppress T cell-mediated antiviral effects. The immunological responses of 113 COVID-19 patients with mild (non-ICU) and severe (ICU) illness were serially examined in 2020. Patients' immune profiles showed a general increase in innate cell lineages and a concurrent reduction of T cells. The plasma levels of IFNs and cytokines were associated with the nasopharyngeal viral load of the infected individuals. Patients who were on antibiotics saw a slower drop in viral load. (Coperchini *et al.*, 2020, and Lucas *et al.*, 2020).

Additionally, researchers discovered a link between early, increased cytokines and poorer illness outcomes. Patients with mild COVID-19 illness showed a steady decline in type 1 & 3 (antiviral and antifungal, respectively) innate immune responses after an initial rise in cytokines. Patients with severe disease, on the other hand, continued to exhibit these increased responses during the course of their illness. Multiple type 2 (anti-helminths) innates immune response indicators, including as IL-5, IL-13, IgE, and eosinophils, increased along with the severe illness. The results of highlight the significance of early immunological therapies that focus on inflammatory indicators that are predictive of severe symptoms rather than late-appearing cytokines. An essential factor that may be utilized to forecast survival rates and, at certain phases of disease development, is the T cell mediated immune response. T cell suppression, such as that seen in SARS and MERS, is common in respiratory virus infections.

Beyond the presumptions, recent investigations revealed that T cell suppression is a characteristic linked to every stage of COVID-19, even asymptomatic individuals, pointing directly to a SARS-CoV-2 as its genesis. Further blood analysis of the COVID-19 patients revealed that elevated levels of cytokines, such as TNF-, IL-6, IL-8, and IL-10, were negatively correlated to T cell counts in severe COVID-19, suggesting that, in addition to direct SARS-CoV-2 mediated

virulence, high levels of these cytokines may also be a contributing factor to T cell suppression. The anti-inflammatory protein IL-10, which is both immunosuppressive and may cause T cell fatigue, was shown to be abnormally elevated in severe COVID-19 cases, while it was only elevated in convalescent patients with SARS. Severe COVID-19 was also discovered to have high levels of cell death markers such PD-1 and TIM-3, which are markers of T cell exhaustion. In order to improve viral clearance in a respiratory infection, an early IFN-I driven innate immune response is thought to be important. Respiratory viruses, such SARS-CoV-1 and MERS-CoV, which may improve their infectivity and persist in the host tissue, use strategies that delay or reduce the host's IFN-I driven innate immune response. Surprisingly, it was discovered that SARS-CoV-2, an influenza virus of type A (IVA), used a highly unique technique to subvert the host's innate immune response. Recent investigations using SARS-CoV-2 in cell culture demonstrated a reduced IFN-I and III response but surprisingly, a substantially elevated cytokine response. A viral protein ORF3b was discovered to be the mediator of the attenuation of the early IFN response.

However, a recent work is the first to suggest a pathological foundation for it. They discovered clear atrophy or lack of germinal centers in the lymphoid tissues, causing individuals with severe COVID-19 illness to produce antibodies from developed B cells (or plasma cells) as early as 10 days after the onset of symptoms. The selection of high-affinity B cells with a long lifetime depends on the presence of germinal centers in the lymphoid tissues, which is critical. In contrast to coronaviruses, some infectious diseases have antibody-mediated immune responses that last much longer (for decades). These immune responses not only guarantee that people are protected from re-infection but can also help create herd immunity when a significant portion of a population is infected. As a result, COVID-19's short-lived

viral-specific antibodies suggest that achieving herd immunity may be challenging. To create a functioning replicase complex and promote viral dissemination, coronaviruses need the virally encoded enzyme papain-like protease (PLpro), also known as NSP3. The cleavage of proteinaceous post-translational changes on host proteins by PLpro is another way for the virus to evade host defenses against it. Additionally, SCoV2-PLpro helped ISG15 separate from IFN responsive factor 3 (IRF3) after infection and reduced type I IFN responses. Importantly, SCoV2-PLpro inhibition with GRL-0617 decreased the cytopathogenic impact of the virus, promoted the antiviral interferon pathway, and inhibited viral replication in infected cells (Victora & Nussenzweig, 2012, Channappanavar *et al.*, 2014, Newton *et al.*, 2016, Channappanavar *et al.*, 2019, Shin *et al.*, 2020, Lucas *et al.*, 2020, Zhang *et al.*, 2020, Sun *et al.*, 2020, Diao *et al.*, 2020, Blanco-Melo *et al.*, 2020, Konno *et al.*, 2020, Kaneko *et al.*, 2020, Wu *et al.*, 2020).

3- SARS-CoV-2 spike proteins facilitate host cell invasion and escape from detection

Additionally, recent publications provided evidence that SARS-CoV-2 proteins have a direct role in mediating host cell invasion. In order to start an infection, viral spike protein catalyzes the fusing of the viral and host cell membranes. SARS-CoV-2 spike protein occurs in two different forms, which correspond to its prefusion (2.9 resolution) and post fusion (3.0 resolution) conformations, as shown by using cryo-EM 33. Moreover, they demonstrated how the post fusion structure of the S2 subunit of the spike protein was strategically decorated by N-linked glycans, indicating that this form may play protective roles against host immune responses (it may induce non-neutralizing antibody responses to subvert the host immune system) and shield from adverse environmental conditions. The discovery, that the SARS-CoV-2 spike protein may reside in two structural forms in the host cells, is very significant for the development of vaccines

that primarily target spike protein and for post-infection immunity. (Cai *et al.*, 2020m and Shi *et al.*, 2022).

4- SARS-CoV-2 mimics an epithelial ion channel to hijack host cell machinery

Figure 2.5: SARS-CoV-2 drives host cell molecular pathways.

Note: adapted from (Kumar *et al.*, 2020).

The S1/S2 cleavage site of the spike protein (S) of SARS-CoV-2 exhibits a remarkable protein sequence resemblance to the furin-cleavable peptide region on the human epithelial sodium channel -subunit (ENaC- α), according to research by the SARS-CoV-2 spike protein segment's structural similarity to ENaC- α meant that the virus infected cells may compete for the available FURIN, which could thwart

ENaC- α 's proteolytic activation (Figure 2.5). According to the writings, ENaC- α plays significant roles in ARDS caused by cytokines and chemokines in inflammatory illnesses. A deregulation of ENaC- α mediated by SARS-CoV-2 may have significant effects on the occurrence of ARDS in very ill COVID-19 patients. SARS-imitation CoV-2's of ENaC- α in lung epithelial cells may also be related to a problem that has not yet been addressed in COVID-19 patients: the contribution of smoking to virus-caused lung damage. However, the pathogenic processes causing this remain mostly understood. Recent work does reveal a greater risk of severe complications and increased death among smokers hospitalized with COVID-19. Existing research indicates that cigarette smoke condensate, specifically its main component Crotonaldehyde (CRO), can cause dose-dependent inhibition of ENaC- α subunit expression in pneumocytes, resulting in edematous acute lung injury; consequently, the addition of SARS-CoV-2 infection could only make the condition worse. (Anand *et al.*, 2020), (Mutchler & Kleyman, 2019, Wynne *et al.*, 2017), (Alqahtani *et al.*, 2020), (Li *et al.*, 2017), (Xu *et al.*, 2007).

2.1.f – Pathophysiology of COVID-19

The pathophysiology of COVID-19 infection, from molecular to clinical manifestation, may be shown in (figure 2.6) and (figure 2.7). Below is a short description of each phase.

Asymptomatic phase

The upper respiratory tract's nasal epithelial cells are where the SARS-CoV-2, which is acquired by respiratory aerosols, binds. Along with infecting ciliated cells in the conducting airways, the virus replicates and spreads locally. The immunological response produced at this stage, which lasts a few days, is quite mild. (Sims *et al.*, 2005).

Invasion and infection of the upper respiratory tract

By means of the conducting airways, the virus is now migrating from the nasal epithelium to the upper respiratory tract. The illness presents with symptoms of fever, lethargy, and dry cough due to upper airway involvement. The production of interferons (IFN- β and IFN- γ) and C-X-C motif chemokine ligand 10 (CXCL-10) from virus-infected cells contributes to a stronger immune response at this phase (Tang *et al.*, 2005).

Involvement of the lower respiratory tract and progression to acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS)

The illness progresses to this stage in around one-fifth of all infected individuals, who then have severe symptoms. Viral replication begins after the virus reaches type 2 alveolar epithelial cells through the host receptor ACE-2 and begins to create new viral nucleocapsids. The virus-laden pneumocytes now release a variety of cytokines and inflammatory markers, including CXCL-10, monocyte chemoattractant protein-1 (MCP-1), macrophage inflammatory protein-1 (MIP-1), tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α), and IFN- β . These include interleukins (IL-1, IL-6, IL-8, IL-120, and IL-12). The neutrophils, CD4 helper T cells, and CD8 cytotoxic T cells that are chemoattracted by this "cytokine storm" start to get sequestered in the lung tissue. These cells are in charge of warding off the virus, but in doing so, they also cause inflammation and lung damage (Xu *et al.*, 2020).

Figure 2.6: Pathophysiology steps from early to fatality.

Note: from (Lee & Choi, 2021)

Figure 2.7: Collective pathophysiology and symptomatology of COVID-19

Note: adapted from (News-Medical.net, 2020)

2.2 COVID-19 and Oral Health

There has been substantial research on the incidence of oral health issues in individuals who have COVID-19 infection as well as their relationships to the severity and mortality of the infection. With a frequency of 41.0%, dry mouth is the most prevalent oral health issue among people with COVID-19 infection, followed by oral lesions (38.8%), orofacial discomfort (18.3%), and periodontal symptoms (11.7%). Furthermore, COVID-19 severity is correlated with periodontal symptoms, but not COVID-19 positive or mortality.

In the scientific literature, instances of COVID-19 have been linked to dry mouth, oral lesions, and periodontal symptoms. Due to the presence of the ACE2 receptor and TMPRSS2 in the epithelial cells of the oral mucosa and the salivary glands, which permit viral replication and may cause inflammation and the degeneration of oral tissue, recent studies have suggested that the oral cavity is potentially highly susceptible to COVID-19 infection. SARS-CoV-2 was discovered in the periodontal tissue of seven COVID-19 fatality victims during a post-mortem investigation. The oral mucous membrane and salivary glands also include ACE2 receptors, which may contribute to COVID-19 infection and eventual dysfunction. The function of oral keratinocytes and the epithelial lining of the salivary gland ducts may be disrupted by the interaction of SARS-CoV-2 and ACE2 and the subsequent cleavage by TMPRSS2 enzyme, which has the potential to cause diseases affecting oral health. The included research show that there may be a direct link between COVID-19 infection and the beginning of oral health issues. However, a variety of circumstances, including COVID-19-related stress and/or emotional reaction, intubation, medicine, and immunological problems, might result in oral health concerns.

Oral lesions are thought to be a sign of ongoing immunological storm-related damage following SARS-CoV-2 eradication, which may be made worse by an elevation of inflammatory markers brought on by the virus. In severe COVID-19 patients, antibiotic therapy has often been employed as a therapeutic and prophylactic approach. The positive results suggest that SARS-CoV-2 and other pathogenic pathogens may co-infect the oral cavity. As a result, while causation may be difficult to establish, oral microbiota rearrangement after antibiotic therapy may predispose individuals to the development of oral health issues. Future research is required to clarify the relationship between COVID-19 infection and oral health issues, taking into account SARS-etiology COV-2's and direct action, the influence of the inflammatory response on dental homeostasis, and the effects of antibiotic or other therapies. Due to the novelty and severity of the COVID-19 pandemic throughout the study periods, the inconsistent methodologies are probably a reflection of the expenses and challenges associated with conducting oral health examinations. (AbuBakr *et al.*, 2012, Biadsee *et al.*, 2020, Fantozzi *et al.*, 2020, Xu *et al.*, 2020, Huang *et al.*, 2021, Pascolo *et al.*, 2020, Fernandes Matuck *et al.*, 2020, Morris *et al.*, 2020, Sampson *et al.*, 2020, Santos *et al.*, 2020, Mo *et al.*, 2020, and Gherlone *et al.*, 2021).

The severity of COVID-19, a marker for immunological dysregulation that has been associated to thrombosis and multi-organ failure affecting the brain, heart, and kidneys, was shown to have a substantial correlation with periodontal symptoms, in contrast. Many theories have been put forward, despite the fact that it is unclear how periodontal problems in individuals with COVID-19 infection may affect them. The possible contribution of cytokines to the severity of COVID-19 was recently reviewed. It should be noted that interleukin-6 (IL-6), interleukin-8 (IL-8), and Tumor Necrosis Factors (TNF), which have been linked to significant

interferons and a cytokine storm, may all rise in response to periodontal symptoms. Patients with COVID-19 have received anti-inflammatory therapeutic therapies include corticosteroids, IL-6 inhibitors, and monoclonal antibody medications.

Recent research has revealed that oral illness may worsen COVID-19 severity through two additional mechanisms in addition to conventional inflammatory pathways. First, a rise in viral respiratory infections and aspiration pneumonia have both been linked to periodontopathic bacteria. In addition, older adults 65 and older represent a high-risk group for the severity of COVID-19 due to potential chronic comorbidities and weakened immune systems. Furthermore, oral health conditions that affect older adults share common risk factors with PD, such as poor oral hygiene, long-term medication use, and co-occurring chronic diseases (Tanaka *et al.*, 2016, Müller *et al.*, 2017, Jose & Manuel, 2020, Rapkiewicz *et al.*, 2020, Molayem & Pontes, 2020, Jahanshahlu & Rezaei, 2020, Duesberg *et al.*, 2022b).

2.3 Immunological Response to SARS-CoV-2 Virus

Since SARS-CoV-2 is a novel human pathogen, it is reasonable to anticipate that it will take two to three weeks after first encounter for an adequate adaptive immune response capable of neutralizing novel antigens to emerge. This quick chronology suggests that the innate immune response, whose activation is independent of antibodies and/or T cells, is responsible for infection management in individuals with asymptomatic or moderate illness. A failure of nonspecific first-line defensive systems or the emergence of an acquired immunological response that, if increased, might become harmful to the host, especially in the context of pertinent comorbidities, may be the cause of severe manifestations of the illness. (Okba *et al.*, 2020).

2.3.a – Innate immunity

The SARS-CoV-2 innate immune response The complement and fibrinolysis systems, soluble proteins that identify glycans on cell surfaces (such as Mannose Binding Lectin [MBL]), Interferons (IFNs), chemokines, and spontaneously occurring antibodies are among the humoral components of antiviral innate immunity (mainly IgM but also IgA and IgG). It also contains a number of biological components, including gamma delta T cells, innate lymphoid cells (ILCs), and Natural Killer (NK) cells, which often prevent viral infections from spreading by acting cytotoxically on target cells, producing cytokines, and inducing an adaptive response (Boechat *et al.*, 2021).

Components of innate immune response involved in SARS-CoV-2 immunity are:

1- Natural antibodies.

Similar to naturally occurring ABO antibodies, anti-glycan antibodies may be found in serum and are thus detectable even in the absence of previous vaccination. They mostly fall within the IgM class, similar to ABO antibodies. Natural IgM levels are lower in males and those with blood type A, and they decline dramatically with age (>40 years), which is similar to some of the patterns of clinical severity in COVID-19.

(“ABO Blood Group and Susceptibility to Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome,” 2005, Zhao *et al.*, 2020).

2- Complement system.

The innate immune response to viruses relies heavily on the complement system, but it may also set off pro-inflammatory reactions. MBL, one of the complement system's components in innate immunity, is a soluble pattern-recognition receptor that detects mannose residues in a variety of bacteria' membranes (PRR). This identification triggers the complement

system, which increases phagocytosis and causes inflammation. (Zhou *et al.*, 2010, Tomaiuolo *et al.*, 2012),

3- SARS-CoV-2 viral PRR sensing:

A variety of innate immune cells, such as macrophages, monocytes, dendritic cells, Neutrophils, and Innate Lymphoid Cells (ILCs), including Natural Killer (NK) cells, are equipped with a variety of PRRs that can recognize Pathogen Associated Molecular Patterns (PAMPs) or Damage-Associated Molecular Patterns (DAMPs) and trigger inflammatory signaling pathways and immune responses. The Toll-like receptor (TLR), Retinoic Acid-Inducible Gene I (RIG-I)-like receptor (RLR), Nucleotide-Binding Oligomerization domain (NOD)-like receptor (NLR), C-type lectin receptor, and Absent In Melanoma 2 (AIM2)-like receptor (ALR), families are the five major PRR families. (Kanneganti, 2020).

4- Cytokine signaling, cell death and cytokine storm:

IFNs and other pro-inflammatory cytokines are released simultaneously by the SARS-CoV-2 PRR signaling. Patients with COVID-19 have increased levels of the expression of certain pro-inflammatory cytokines and IFNs, such as IL-1, IL-6, TNF, IL-12, IFN-, IFN-, IL-17, and others. These cytokines support cellular homeostasis while also assisting in the eradication of infections. As an example, momentary activation of inflammatory cytokine receptors, namely IL-1 signaling, promotes insulin production from pancreatic beta cells, enabling the beta cell to adjust to the increased insulin demand under stress. Cytokine storm, a potentially fatal illness brought on by excessive cytokine synthesis driven by inflammatory cell death, is nevertheless exacerbated by the dysregulated release of pro-

inflammatory cytokines (PANoptosis). TNF and IFN- work together to signal and cause inflammatory cell death (PANoptosis) in the setting of COVID-19, which aids in disease pathogenesis. Pyroptosis, apoptosis, and necroptosis are unable to explain this cell death mechanism. When TNF and IFN- work together to cause noptosis, signal transducer and activator of transcription (STAT)1 and IRF1 signaling are required, which in turn activates caspase-8 to cause cell death. TNF and IFN- signaling together cause a fatal shock syndrome in mice, which is similar to the cytokine storm seen in certain COVID-19 patients. TNF and IFN-specific blocking antibodies have been shown to lower mortality in SARS-CoV-2-infected mice as well as in other cytokine storm models.

Depletion of germinal centers in the spleen and lymph nodes, another characteristic of COVID-19, may be caused by lymphocyte cell death induced by TNF and IFN- signaling. High levels of TNF are found in the remaining germinal centers of patients with severe COVID-19, which may limit B cell affinity maturation, isotype switching, and production of mature antibodies, having a negative impact on patient outcomes. TNF and IFN-shock can also cause lymphopenia and immunosuppression. Overall, cytokine release must be regulated to avoid a systemic cytokine storm and pathogenic inflammation during SARS-CoV-2 infection, even though cytokines are essential for the innate immune response and the effective clearance of viral infections, (Zohar *et al.*, 2020, Lee *et al.*, 2021, Karki *et al.*, 2021).

2.3.b – Adaptive immunity

B cells, CD4+ T cells, and CD8+ T cells are the three main cell types that make up the adaptive immune system. B cells makes an antibody. A variety of helper and effector capabilities are present in CD4+ T cells. Infected cells are killed by CD8+ T lymphocytes. Understanding adaptive immune responses to SARS-CoV-2 is essential because these responses are crucial for the prevention and treatment of practically all viral infections that cause illness in humans. Adaptive immune responses and immunological memory are also essential for the effectiveness of all vaccinations.

Elements of adaptive immune response involved in SARS-CoV-2 immunity are:

1- Model of immune responses to SARS-CoV-2

The innate immune system quickly detects an idealized case of a general viral infection, setting off the "alarm bells" of type I IFN production and associated molecules. This may happen a few hours after infection, (Murphy *et al.*, 2022).

Three key goals of the innate immune response are as follows: (1) limiting viral multiplication inside infected cells, (2) establishing an antiviral environment in the local tissue, including enlisting innate immune system effector cells, and (3) activating the adaptive immune response. The innate immune system's first two functions reduce the rate of viral reproduction and dissemination. A crucial condition for the innate immune system to launch the adaptive immune response is the third. The fundamental necessity of choosing and growing virus-specific cells from the sizable pools of naïve B cells and T cells specific for various molecular structures and sequences (>10⁹ cells each), is due to slow down adaptive immune responses because of the intrinsic time requirements for significant proliferation and effector cell differentiation,

adaptive immune responses take 6–10 days after priming to create enough cells to suppress a viral infection. When sufficient numbers of effector T cells (helper T cells and cytotoxic T cells) and effector B cells (antibody-secreting cells, also known as plasma blasts and plasma cells), have multiplied and differentiated, they frequently cooperate to quickly and effectively eliminate infected cells and circulating virions. Before the innate immunological alarms are raised, the adaptive immune responses are not prepared.

According to a straightforward model, in a typical case of COVID-19, a temporal delay in the innate immune responses is sufficient to cause asymptomatic infection, which accounts for 40% of SARS-CoV-2 infections, or clinically mild disease (where "mild" refers to the COVID-19 clinical definition of not requiring hospitalization). This is because the T cell and antibody responses happen relatively quickly and control the infection. T cells and antibodies are linked to the successful resolution of typical COVID-19 patients. SARS-CoV-2-specific T cell responses have been found to be significantly associated with milder disease in studies of acute and convalescent COVID-19 patients, suggesting that T cell responses may be crucial for control and resolution of a primary SARS-CoV-2 infection.

The virus gets a head start in replication in the upper respiratory tract (URT) and lungs if the innate immune response is delayed for too long. If this happens due to particularly effective virus evasion, poor innate immunity, or a combination of both, the virus also fails to prime an adaptive immune response for an extended period of time, which can result in conditions that are severe enough to cause lung disease that requires hospitalization. (Oran & Topol, 2020).

2- CD4+ T cells

Nearly all SARS-CoV-2 infections are followed by the detection of T cell responses. According to studies, CD4+ T cell responses to SARS-CoV-2 are more noticeable than CD8+ T cell responses and have been linked to the prevention of primary SARS-CoV-2 infection. In animal models, CD4+ T cells more so than CD8+ T cells were linked to the prevention of SARS-CoV infection. Any viral protein-specific T cells may be important for enhancing protective immunity. However, given that almost all prospective COVID-19 vaccines only include Spike, there is special interest in T cell responses to SARS-CoV-2 Spike protein (also known as "Spike"). Additionally, Spike-specific CD4+ T cells are required for the production of anti-Spike antibodies, with potential contributions from CD4+ T cells that are specific for other virion structural proteins. The most common targets of SARS-CoV-2-specific CD4+ T cells are spike, M, and nucleocapsid, with significant responses also seen against ORF3a and nsp3. M is a relatively small, multipass transmembrane protein that does not appear to be recognized by high-affinity class II restricted T cells in the naive repertoire. This suggests that M is either highly expressed *in vivo* or made available to CD4+ T cells in an immunogenic environment. Spike is the SARS-CoV-2 antigen that has been identified as being the most frequently; however, a "megapool" of predicted class II epitopes measures 50% of the SARS-CoV-2-specific CD4+ T cell response outside of Spike (Gri Although ORF7/8 CD4+ T cell responses may show relative preference towards the acute phase, patterns of CD4+ T cell SARS-CoV-2 antigens identified seem to be comparable throughout acute infection, convalescence, and memory phases (Mateus *et al.*, 2020, Nelde *et al.*, 2021).

3- CD4+ T cells in acute COVID-19

SARS-CoV-2-specific CD4+ T cells may be seen as early as days 2-4 post-symptom onset (PSO), convalescent patients are more likely to have them than acute cases. Notably, compared to antibodies and CD8+ T cells, SARS-CoV-2-specific CD4+ T cells demonstrated the highest correlation with decreased COVID-19 disease severity. Acute COVID-19's rapid production of SARS-CoV-2-specific CD4+ T cells was linked to a mild illness and hastened viral clearance. On the other hand, severe or deadly COVID-19 (>day 22 PSO in some patients) was related with the startlingly prolonged absence of SARS-CoV-2-specific CD4+ T cells (Braun *et al.*, 2020, and Weiskopf *et al.*, 2020).

4- CD4+ T cell functions in SARS-CoV-2 infection

The ability of CD4+ T cells to develop into a variety of helper and effector cell types allows them to guide B cells, assist CD8+ T cells, recruit innate cells, directly combat viruses, and aid in tissue repair. Virus-specific CD4+ T cells often develop into T follicular helper cells and Th1 cells (Tfh). IFN γ and other associated cytokines are produced by Th1 cells, which have antiviral properties. The establishment of memory B cells, long-lasting humoral immunity, and most neutralizing antibody responses depends on Tfh cells, which are specialized B cell helpers. During acute SARS-CoV-2 infection, circulating Tfh cells (cTfh) specific for SARS-CoV-2 are produced. Additionally, SARS-CoV-2 memory cTfh cells are produced. SARS-CoV-2 cTfh cell frequencies have been linked to decreased illness severity, even while neutralizing antibody titers have not. It should be noted that a significant portion of SARS-CoV-2 cTfh are CCR6+, which may be a sign of mucosal airway homing and has been shown for the common cold coronavirus HKU1.

CD4⁺ T cells support CD8⁺ T cell responses in addition to antibody responses. Although the precise CD4⁺ T cells that are helping the CD8⁺ T cells are yet unknown, IL-21, which is a typical cytokine of TFH cells, may be crucial for CD4⁺ T cells helping CD8⁺ T cells. Even while supporting B cells and CD8⁺ T cells is one of their key roles, CD4⁺ T cells may also develop into effector cells with more direct anti-pathogen actions, including Th1 cells. Mice are shielded from fatal SARS-CoV infection by IFN γ , CD4⁺ T cells. IFN γ is the predominant cytokine produced by SARS-CoV-2-specific CD4⁺ T cells from COVID-19 patients, with a distinct IFN γ , tumor necrosis factor (TNF), and IL-2 protein signature of canonical Th1 cells. Related cell types called CD4-CTLs have direct cytotoxic action and are linked to defense against several serious viral infections. Although the cytotoxicity degranulation marker CD107a has only seldom been detected on SARS-CoV-2-specific CD4⁺ T cells, a CD4-CTL transcriptional signature has been identified. One of CD4⁺ T cells' jobs is to attract other effector cells to a region of viral antigen, and SARS-CoV-2-specific CD4⁺ T cells' production of the chemokines CCL3/4/5 (MIP-1 s) and XCL1 may aid in this process (Buchholz and Busch, 2019; Zander *et al.*, 2019, Crotty, 2019, Lednicky *et al.*, 2021, Juno *et al.*, 2020; Neidleman *et al.*, 2020; Sekine *et al.*, 2020, Piccoli *et al.*, 2020; Robbiani *et al.*, 2020).

A chemokine receptor called CCR6 is linked to migration to mucosal tissues. Although undetectable or low levels of IL-17a protein expression have been observed, CCR6 expression by a subset of SARS-CoV-2 specific CD4⁺ T cells may suggest underlying Th17 characteristics of those. Contrarily, SARS-CoV-2 specific CD4⁺ T cells seem to express IL-22

strongly, which can also be produced by mucosal CD4⁺ T cells. In other infections, CCR6⁺ IL-22⁺ and CCR6⁺ IL-17⁺ cells may function essentially independently of one another. In particular, lung and gut epithelial cells are tightly linked to tissue repair by IL-22, raising the possibility that the SARS-CoV-2 CD4⁺ T cell response may actively take part in lung tissue healing during COVID-19. SARS-CoV-2 memory CD4⁺ T cells still seem to be able to produce IL-22. The possible immunological deviation to Th2 and immunopathogenesis were first of significant concern, however SARS-CoV-2-specific CD4⁺ T cells from patients consistently lack Th2 features cells (Dudakov *et al.*, 2015, Morou *et al.*, 2019, Peeples, 2020).

5- CD8⁺ T cells

Due to their capacity to eradicate infected cells, CD8⁺ T cells are essential for the recovery from many viral infections. The presence of virus-specific CD8⁺ T lymphocytes has been linked to improved COVID-19 outcomes in SARS-CoV-2 infections. The prevalence of circulating SARS-CoV-2-specific CD8⁺ T cells is often lower than that of CD4⁺ T cells. Predicted HLA class I epitope peptides can recognize a significant portion of the CD8 T cell response that is unique to the SARSCOV-2 virus. Spike, nucleocapsid, M, and ORF3a are prominent SARSCoV-2 antigens for which SARS-CoV-2 CD8⁺ T cells are specific. SARS-CoV-2-specific CD8⁺ T cell responses may emerge quickly during acute COVID-19, similar to SARSCoV-2-specific CD4⁺ T cell responses, with reports of virus-specific CD8⁺ T cells as early as day 1 PSO. SARS-CoV-2-specific CD8⁺ T cells in acute COVID-19 have large amounts of molecules linked to powerful cytotoxic effector activities, including IFN γ , granzyme B, perforin, and

CD107a. The expression patterns of memory CD8⁺ T cells for SARS-CoV-2 are identical (Grifoni *et al.*, 2020; Zuo *et al.*, 2020).

6- Antibodies and B cells

Almost 90% of SARS-CoV-2 infected people seroconvert by day 10 PSO, with the majority doing so between 5 and 15 days after exposure. Spike and nucleocapsid are the main antigens that are looked at for seroconversion. Spike immunoglobulin G (IgG) titers and nucleocapsid titers are closely connected. The receptor binding domain (RBD) of Spike is the target of >90% of neutralizing antibodies in COVID-19 cases, with some neutralizing antibodies instead targeting the N-terminal domain (NTD). Spike is the target of SARS-CoV-2. In big investigations, the estimates of seroconversion to SARS-CoV-2 Spike vary from 91% to 99%. Infected people see simultaneous spikes in IgG, IgA, and IgM antibodies (Isho *et al.*, 2020; Premkumar *et al.*, 2020; Suthar *et al.*, 2020, Ripperger *et al.*, 2020; Gudbjartsson *et al.*, 2020; Liu *et al.*, 2020).

In most SARS-CoV-2-infected individuals, neutralizing antibodies form quickly at the same time as seroconversion. B cells with a variety of heavy chain and light chain V genes create the neutralizing antibodies. Neutralizing antibodies against SARS-CoV-2 also show little to no somatic hypermutation. These findings together suggest that it is extremely simple for B cells to produce neutralizing antibodies against SARS-CoV-2 with little to no affinity maturation. Additionally, the findings show that SARS-CoV-2 neutralizing antibody responses often originate from naïve B cells rather than from previously existing cross-reactive memory B cells. As a result, neutralizing epitopes on the SARSCoV-2 RBD domain, especially those that

match the ACE2 receptor binding footprint, seem to be highly immunogenic and simple for antibodies to identify. The fact that circulating SARS-CoV-2 neutralizing antibody titers are relatively low in a significant portion of recovered COVID-19 cases, however, should also be taken into consideration. This suggests that either the neutralizing antibody potency or the serum concentration in this subset is suboptimal. (Rogers *et al.*, 2020, Gaebler *et al.*, 2021; Anderson *et al.*, 2020; Ng *et al.*, 2020; Nguyen-Contant *et al.*, 2020; Shrock *et al.*, 2020; Wajnberg *et al.*, 2020, Dan *et al.*, 2021).

Antibodies may destroy virally infected cells in addition to stopping viruses from spreading outside of cells, as was mentioned above, and this may be a key mode of action *in vivo*. However, Fc receptor-associated functions in serum were correlated with protective immunity in a SARS-CoV-2 NHP vaccine model, neutralizing antibodies with Fc-receptor binding capacity were more protective in mice, and humans who did not survive COVID-19 infection had antibody responses with reduced Fc-dependent antibody effector activity. However, there is currently no direct evidence of this in human SARS-CoV-2. Increased antigen load often leads to higher antibody titers in a variety of animal models. This seems to be the case with SARS-CoV-2, as shown by the extensive cohort studies showing a significant correlation between COVID-19 illness severity and neutralizing antibody titers (and overall Spike antibody titers). Middle Eastern respiratory disease (MERS) and SARS were both seen in a similar manner.

The interplay between Tfh cells, neutralizing antibodies, and the severity of COVID-19 illness seems to be intricate. According to various studies, SARS-CoV-2-specific Tfh cells have varying correlations, although high neutralizing antibody titers are related with severe illness and perhaps extrafollicular B cell responses. According, divergent T and B cell responses

may be caused by a disconnect between B cell and T cell responses as a result of the altered early innate immune response, which may cause kinetic delays or dysregulation of T cell priming. More long-term investigations on the dynamics of antibody and virus-specific T cell responses during acute SARS-CoV-2 infections with varied illness severity are needed to close these knowledge gaps. (Benhnia *et al.*, 2009, Yu *et al.*, 2020, Sariol and Perlman, 2020, Woodruff *et al.*, 2020, Moderbacher *et al.*, 2020; Arunachalam *et al.*, 2020; Schafer *et al.*, 2021).

2.3.c – Mucosal Immunity

As SARS-CoV-2 initially primarily affects the upper respiratory tract (URT), mucosal immune responses are anticipated to be induced in the nasopharynx through the tonsils and adenoids, which are collectively known as nasopharynx-associated lymphoid tissue (NALT), which serve as inductive sites for the mucosal immune system. Although it is unclear how much these sites contribute to mucosal immune responses in people, it is plausible that responses might also be generated by mucosal inductive sites in the lacrimal duct, or the oral cavity. Adult humans do not often have bronchus-associated lymphoid tissue (BALT), although it may be detected in children and adolescents and may be brought on by infections. This raises intriguing concerns about whether responses elicited in BALT can help explain why young individuals have been shown to be more resistant to COVID-19 illness, or if BALT might be activated by SARS-CoV-2 with implications for the progression of infection. All of these mucosal inductive site tissues produce mucosal B cells

capable of generating IgA, which migrate to distinct distant mucosal effector sites and undergo a process of differentiation into polymeric (p) IgA-secreting plasma cells. Additionally, tonsils also produce systemic IgG-producing B cells, which settle in peripheral lymphoid organs and undergo differentiation before secreting IgG for circulation (Tschernig & Pabst, 2000, Boyaka *et al.*, 2005, Czerkinsky *et al.*, 2011, O'Sullivan & Montgomery, 2015, Russell *et al.*, 2020)

Mucosal plasma cells create pIgA in the subepithelial spaces of the mucosae and related glands, which is then preferentially transported into the secretions via the polymeric immunoglobulin receptor-mediated route and released as sIgA. The virus comes into contact with a sIgA-dominated environment both in the nasal passages and as it descends into the trachea and bronchi, which is produced by the mucosal immune system and maintains an essentially non-inflammatory milieu. However, as it enters the terminal airways and alveoli, it finds itself in a setting where IgG produced by the circulation predominates. Antibodies that may neutralize viruses, particularly circulating antibodies, have received the most attention. The mucosal surfaces where the virus is present must be reached for these to be useful in preventing infection or illness, and it should be highlighted that circulating IgA, even in polymeric form, is not efficiently carried into secretions. While plasma-derived IgG is present in the upper respiratory tract (URT) and particularly the lower respiratory tract (LRT), IgG is inflammatory in its mode of action due to the activation of complement and the involvement of phagocytes like neutrophils and macrophages as well as natural killer (NK) cells. The terminal airways of the lungs are where COVID-19's severe disease manifests itself, and there, circulating IgG is the predominate immunoglobulin. Multiple molecular and cellular components, including cells attracted by virus-induced chemoattractants, contribute to the severe inflammation that results. The cellular component of the

adaptive immune response, which consists of CD4+ and cytotoxic CD8+ T cells, may also be transported to the alveoli by circulation. However, since they kill diseased cells, cytotoxic cells are unable to stop an infection from spreading. They can only stop it from happening in the first place.

The majority of COVID-19 vaccine development efforts center on systemic injection, which primarily produces circulatory IgG antibodies and may also result in cytotoxic T cells. These methods are ineffective in triggering mucosal immune reactions, which can only be brought on by mucosal immunization methods, such as the NALT in the URT. Due to the fact that the distribution of the responses relies on the actual mechanism of induction, mucosal immune responses are partially compartmentalized. For instance, the nasal route mostly causes reactions in the respiratory system and salivary glands, while the enteric route primarily causes responses in the gastro-intestinal tract. The homing receptors, which include specific integrins and chemokine receptors specific for the target tissues, imprint the T and B cells that are stimulated in the corresponding inductive sites, the gut associated lymphoid tissues (GALT, such as the intestinal Peyer's patches), or the non-lymphoid tissues (NALT), explaining the reasons for these differential distributions. Practically speaking, this suggests that intranasal vaccination should be a successful method of inducing primarily sIgA antibody responses in the URT and LRT, where SARS-CoV-2 might be neutralized and removed without triggering inflammatory effects. Additionally, it suggests that detecting IgA antibodies in nasal secretions or saliva should be a more accurate approach to evaluate the effectiveness of immune responses against SARS-CoV-2, regardless of whether they are brought on by intranasal vaccination or a naturally occurring illness. While of further importance, measuring serum IgA antibodies is not a replacement since serum IgA is derived from a different source (mostly the bone marrow) and primarily consists of

monomeric IgA1. This is different from mucosal sIgA, which has both subclasses and is produced locally in the lamina propria by pIgA-secreting plasma cells that live in mucosal tissues and glands. By means of processes including neutralization, reduction of adhesion to and penetration of epithelial cells, agglutination, and facilitation of clearance in the mucus stream, sIgA antibodies are known to be effective against a variety of pathogens, including viruses.

Viral replication inhibition by intracellular pathways has also been identified. Additionally, sIgA's method of action is virtually non-inflammatory, if not anti-inflammatory. The lectin route relies on the terminal sugar residues in the glycan structures, but IgA does not activate complement through the traditional method and alternative pathway activation by IgA is essentially artificial. Additionally, it has been shown that IgA antibodies may prevent complement activation caused by IgM or IgG antibodies. It's interesting to note that high serum IgA response levels were linked to a greater risk of HIV infection and reduced the protective effect of IgG antibodies with the same antigenic specificity in a human systemic HIV vaccination experiment. It is interesting to note that whereas serum IgA levels grow considerably more slowly and may not reach full adult levels until puberty, mucosal sIgA levels increase fast in newborns and reach adult levels early in infancy. These variations in immune response development should be taken into account given the apparent difference between young children and adults in their vulnerability to COVID-19 illness. Among people of European heritage, where prevalence may reach 1 in 400 people, selective IgA deficiency is quite frequent. Both the mucosal and circulatory compartments are impacted by the deficit, and individuals often exhibit increased vulnerability to URT infections. It is not known if or how COVID-19 is impacted by IgA deficiency.

On the one hand, a lack of sIgA would be predicted to worsen the infection, enabling descent into the LRT and resulting in severe illness, assuming mucosal sIgA antibodies in the URT have a protective effect against the early stages of SARS-CoV-2 infection. Alternately, in LRT infection, when IgG antibodies predominate, a lack of circulating IgA with its ability to obstruct IgM- and IgG-mediated defensive mechanisms may be advantageous. Once again, dysregulated inflammation could be made easier by IgA antibodies' lack of anti-inflammatory regulation. So, IgA deficiency offers a chance to investigate theories on IgA's function in COVID-19. (Bidgood *et al.*, 2014, Baker *et al.*, 2015, Blanco-Melo *et al.*, 2020, Vabret *et al.*, 2020, Fischer, 2020).

2.3.d – Immune escape of SARS-CoV-2

SARS-CoV or MERS-CoV exploit a variety of escape mechanisms, including severe leukopenia and lymphopenia, to subvert the host immune response. These viruses enter the cell and produce a variety of proteins that interact with JAKSTAT and TLR downstream signaling pathways. The accessory proteins from ORFs 4a, 4b, and 5 encoded by the MERS-CoV matrix protein directly suppress the nuclear localization of IRF3 and the IFN promoter. The nonstructural proteins of SARSCoV, PLpro and ORF3b, impede IRF3 phosphorylation and, therefore, its translocation to the nucleus. PLpro is encoded by SARS-CoV and MERS-CoV. These viral accessory proteins also block the JAK-STAT pathway, which prevents ISRE promoters from activating genes. According to a recent study, SARS-CoV-2 infection results in a general reduction in the transcription of antiviral genes because Type I and III interferon production is reduced with adequate ISG expression and chemokine secretion is increased.

The outcomes of COVID-19 tests conducted in vivo and ex vivo were consistent with those discovered in vitro. Consequently, hyperinflammation and a reduction in the innate antiviral response may be two factors contributing to the severity of COVID-19. T cells decline, but SARS-CoV-2 infection also accelerates the depletion of effector T cells, lowering the immunological response to the virus. Increased surface expression of inhibitory receptors like PD-1, TIM-3, and TIGIT as a consequence of cytokines like IL-6, IL-10, and TNF- α or a decline in the number of regulatory T cells cause exhaustion and loss of function in effector T cells (Qin *et al.*, 2021, Blanco-Melo *et al.*, 2020, Diao *et al.*, 2020).

Retention T Cell After the viral/antigen has been eliminated, the majority of the effector T cell dies during the contraction phase. A collection of memory T cells that are trained to combat reinfection is subsequently produced. Cytotoxic memory T cells assist in the destruction of the infected cells after recurrent infection, while CD4⁺ memory T cells stimulate B cells and other immune cells by producing cytokines upon restimulation. Case studies of SARS patients who had recovered revealed that both CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ memory T cells were effective in evoking an immunological response from 3 months to 6 years without the presence of any antigens. In a case study of 23 recovered SARS-CoV patients, memory B cell frequencies were extremely low, while memory T cell responses against the S protein were triggered in 60% of the recovered patients. In the memory T-cell fraction, CD45RA⁺, CCR7⁺, and CD62L⁺ effector memory (CD45RA⁺, CCR7⁺, and CD62L⁺) phenotypes were more prevalent in N-specific helper T cells than in CD8⁺ T cells in a steady-state manner. The research implies that a specific group may be targeted for quick viral clearance using a potent vaccination or T cell epitopes. (Peng *et al.*, 2006, Fan *et al.*, 2009, Lees & Farber, 2010, Tang *et al.*, 2011).

According to recent studies, COVID-19 individuals had lower levels of regulatory T cells and memory T cells. This might exacerbate the inflammatory response, trigger a cytokine storm, and worsen tissue damage and organ failure. Intranasal administration of CD4+ memory T cells as a vaccination conferred a protective response against the human coronavirus in a mouse model but not when administered subcutaneously. In response to the SARSS366 peptide, the injected CD4+ memory T cell generates IFN-g and attracts CD8+ T cells for fast clearance.

Recently, a mouse model that expresses human ACE-2 and mimics human symptoms after intra-nasal SARSCoV-2 infection was created using CRISPR/Cas9 technology. This instrument will be useful for assessing the effectiveness of COVID-19 vaccinations as well as for researching its transmission and pathogenesis (Zhao et al., 2016, and Sun *et al.*, 2020).

2.4 Vaccination

2.4.a Principle of vaccine development

After the public disclosure of the SARS-CoV-2 nucleotide sequence, very efficient vaccinations against the virus were created and put into use. The WHO has now authorized six vaccinations, and more was approved in the following months (WHO Recommendation BioNtech Tozinameran – COVID-19 mRNA Vaccine (Nucleoside Modified) – COMIRNATY®, 2020). The vaccinations cover a range of both conventional and cutting-edge technological platforms. Here, mRNA, adenovirus (a non-replicating viral vector), inactivated entire virion, and protein nanoparticle technologies will be the main topics of discussion.

Based on all of the safety and effectiveness information that is currently available, as well as whether or not it is appropriate for use in low- and middle-income countries, the WHO Emergency Use Listing procedure decides if a product may be advised for use. Utilizing information from clinical trials, manufacturing processes, and quality control procedures, vaccines are evaluated to make sure they satisfy approved criteria of quality, safety, and effectiveness. The evaluation balances any possible dangers against the threat presented by the emergency and the benefit that would result from using the product. Countries are free to provide emergency use authorizations for any health product in accordance with their own national laws and regulations. Authorizations for domestic emergency usage are given at the nations' exclusive discretion; the WHO is not involved (Office of the Commissioner, 2022). The following vaccinations have EUL as of January 12, 2022:

- a. The Pfizer/BioNTech Combined Vaccine, 2020-12-31.
- b. The AstraZeneca/AZD1222 and SII/COVISHIELD vaccines, 16 February 2021.

- c. The Johnson & Johnson-developed Janssen/Ad26.COV 2.S vaccine, 12 March 2021.
- d. The Moderna COVID-19 vaccine, due out on April 30, 2021 (mRNA 1273).
- e. The COVID-19 vaccine from Sinopharm, 7 May 2021.
- f. Sinovac-CoronaVac vaccination, beginning in June 2021.
- g. The BBV152 COVAXIN vaccine, scheduled for release on November 3, 2021.
- h. The Covovax (NVX-CoV2373) vaccination, scheduled for 17 December 2021.
- i. The Nuvaxovid (NVX-CoV2373) vaccine; 20 December 2021

With more than 170 potential vaccines now undergoing clinical trials, the battle against COVID-19 has seen vaccine research advance at a historic rate, see (Figure 2.8). The next part will clarify the fundamental idea by explaining how they vary from one another and how they would shield us from the disease:

1- Whole virus vaccines, to elicit an immune response, several conventional vaccines include whole viruses. There are two primary methods. A virus that is weaker but yet capable of replication is used in live attenuated vaccinations. Viruses used in inactivated vaccines have had their genetic information destroyed, rendering them incapable of reproducing but yet capable of inducing an immune response. Both kinds employ well-established technology and regulatory clearance processes, but live attenuated ones pose a danger of disease transmission to those with weakened immune systems and sometimes need careful cold storage, making their use more difficult in nations with little. People with weakened immune systems may get

inactivated viral vaccinations, although they may also need cold storage resources. (Psichogiou *et al.*, 2021, and Lazarus *et al.*, 2022).

2- Protein subunit vaccines, employ bits of the pathogen, often protein fragments, to elicit an immune response. While doing so reduces the possibility of adverse effects, it also raises the possibility of a poorer immunological response. They often need adjuvants since doing so helps to stimulate the immune system. The hepatitis B vaccine is an example of an existing subunit vaccine, (Heidary *et al.*, 2022).

3- Nucleic acid-based vaccinations: These vaccines rely on genetic material, such as DNA or RNA, to provide cells the instructions they need to produce the antigen. This is often the viral spike protein, as it is in the case of COVID-19. Once inside human cells, this genetic material employs the protein-making machinery to create the antigen that will set off an immune response. These vaccinations have the benefits of being inexpensive and simple to produce. Since a significant amount of the antigen is generated inside our own cells, a robust immune response is expected. The lack of approved DNA or RNA vaccines for human use, however, is a drawback that might make regulatory clearance more difficult. Additionally, RNA vaccines must be stored at very low temperatures, -70C or below, which may be difficult for nations without specialist cold storage facilities, especially low- and middle-income nations. (Qin *et al.*, 2021).

4- Viral vectors vaccine, by providing cells genetic instructions to manufacture antigens, viral vector vaccines also function. However, they vary from nucleic acid vaccines in that they convey these instructions into the cell using a virus that isn't harmful and isn't the goal of the vaccination. The adenovirus, which causes the common cold, is one kind of virus that has often been utilized as a vector. Similar to nucleic acid vaccines, the antigen is produced by our own cells using those instructions in order to elicit an immune response. Since viral vector vaccines may imitate actual viral infection, they ought to strongly elicit an immune response. The vaccination, however, may be less successful since some individuals may already be resistant to the viruses being used as vectors due to the possibility that many have previously been exposed to them. (Travieso *et al.*, 2022).

Types of vaccines	DNA and RNA	Live attenuated	Inactivated	Subunit	Viral vector
How it works	This vaccine uses DNA or RNA molecules to teach the immune system to target key viral proteins.	This is a weakened version of the actual virus.	An inactivated vaccine uses the whole virus after it has been killed with heat or chemicals.	This vaccine uses a piece of a virus' surface to focus your immune system on a single target.	This approach takes a harmless virus and uses it to deliver viral genes to build immunity.
Advantages	Easy and quick to design.	Stimulates a robust immune response without causing serious disease.	Safe because the virus is already dead and is easy to make.	Focuses the immune response on the most important part of the virus for protection and cannot cause infection.	Live viruses tend to elicit stronger immune responses than dead viruses or subunit vaccines.
Disadvantages	Never been done before. There are no licensed DNA or RNA vaccines currently in use.	May not be safe for those with compromised immune systems.	Not as effective as a live virus. Some previous inactivated vaccines have made the disease worse; safety for the novel coronavirus needs to be shown in clinical trials.	May not stimulate a strong response, other chemicals may need to be added to boost long-term immunity.	Important to pick a viral vector that is truly safe. An immune response to the viral vector could make the vaccine less effective.
Existing examples	• None	• Measles, Mumps and Rubella • Chickenpox	• Polio	• Pertussis • Hepatitis B • Human papillomavirus (HPV)	• Ebola • Veterinary medicine
Group testing this approach for COVID-19	• Moderna (RNA) • Inovio (DNA)	• Codagenix • Indian Immunologicals Ltd.	• Sinovac • Sinopharm	• Novavax • AdaptVac	• University of Oxford & AstraZeneca • CanSino Biologics • Johnson & Johnson

Sources: CDC; NIAID; FDA

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Figure 2.8: Type of vaccines based on methodology of development

Adapted from: (CDC, 2022)

2.4.b Role of vaccination in controlling the pandemic

Different degrees of protection against infection, moderate sickness, severe disease, hospitalization, and death are offered by the COVID-19 vaccines with WHO Emergency Use Listings (EUL). Thousands of scientists are doing studies to learn more about how new viral mutations and variations impact the efficacy of the several COVID-19 vaccines. The COVID-19 vaccinations are generally quite efficient at preventing all existing viral types from causing severe disease, hospitalization, and death. They are less efficient than they were for previous virus variations in preventing infection and mild sickness, but if you do get unwell after vaccination, your symptoms are more likely to be mild. Although the COVID-19 vaccinations approved by the WHO are highly successful at lowering your chance of contracting a terrible disease and passing away, keep in mind that no vaccine is 100% effective.

Even those who have received the COVID-19 vaccination might still get sick with the disease in a tiny proportion of cases. The possibility that vaccinated individuals might infect others and spread the virus is still unknown. Due to this, it is crucial to maintain public health and social practices after finishing your vaccinations. A predictive modeling task team created the Mayo Clinic Bayesian SIR model in the early weeks of the COVID-19 pandemic. To assist clinical leaders in understanding the possible immediate and long-term effects of the pandemic on hospital operations, COVID-19 census forecasts was intended to be made available. Since its beginnings, the model has undergone constant revisions to take into account new data sources and the pandemic's changing dynamics, most recently with the incorporation of vaccination. The future of the COVID-19 pandemic will be shaped by vaccination rates, as shown by a number of vaccination scenarios (Figure 2.9), (Storlie *et al.*, 2021).

There are a number of significant limitations to these findings. Our model's uncertainties play a role in these findings, despite the fact that it has so far reliably predicted COVID increases. Given what is currently known, it is expected that immunity established by vaccination and spontaneous infection will diminish, making the population once again susceptible to SARS-CoV-2 infection. The duration of immunity may last between one and two years (on average), according to our best knowledge based on experience with other coronaviruses with some people becoming vulnerable to infection again more quickly than others. The influence of a new virus also has a significant impact on this time period. (Sabino *et al.*, 2021, Stokel-Walker, 2021, Couture *et al.*, 2022).

a.

b.

Figure 2.9: a. Hypothetical case: If nobody received a vaccination, b. Hypothetical scenario: If 75% of the population were vaccinated

Adapted from: (Storlie *et al.*, 2021)

Chapter three

Materials and Methods

3.1 Population and Setting

The current study was performed in the College of Dentistry at the University of Mosul in Mosul, Iraq, samples were gathered, from the vaccination center of Al Salam Teaching Hospital-Mosul City, and from Al Shifaa Quarantine Hospital-Mosul city, between February, 5, 2022 to February, 28, 2022. Participants were enrolled to three study groups. For the purpose of investigating the linked serology among the three study groups see (Table 4-1, and Table 4-2)., the first study group (vaccinated individuals), including 20 peoples who were chosen in the vaccination center of Al Salam Teaching Hospital-Mosul City, those people who had not been infected before, and had the first vaccination and returning to the second booster dose, some were returning to the third booster dose of the mRNA BNT162b2 COVID-19 vaccine (Comirnaty) (Pfizer/BioNTech, New York, NY, USA), (Figure 3.1).

Figure 3.1: - COVID-19 vaccine mRNA BNT162b2 (Comirnaty) (Pfizer/BioNTech, New York, NY, USA)

Adapted from: (<https://www.pharmacypracticenews.com/Covid-19/Article/08-21/Comirnaty-COVID-19-Vaccine-Gets-Unanimous-ACIP-Nod/64549>, n.d.)

The second study population (healthy individuals) including 20 people whom had not been naturally infected with SARS-CoV-2, and were chosen from within the vaccination center of Al Salam hospital, upon visiting in the first time to the center to take the first dose of the mRNA BNT162b2 COVID-19 vaccine Comirnaty (Pfizer/BioNTech, New York, NY, USA).

The third study group (COVID-19 infected individuals) including 15 people who were on going illness of SARS-COV-2 infections, with a documented positive case via quantitative Reverse-Transcriptase Polymerase Chain Reaction (RT-qPCR), who were staying in the RCU (Respiratory care unit) of AlShifaa quarantine hospital-Mosul city, experiencing a range of symptoms at the time of sampling ranging from severe SARS-COV-2 infection to ARDS, (on nasal canula to Bi-pap respiration device), some of the patients were preparing to be discharged from the hospital after achieving completed remission from the disease, 9 patients were on simple bag and canula oxygen continues flow, with average hospital stay of 15 days , 4 patients was in RCU on Bi-Pap device (Munshi and Hall, 2021), with average hospital stay of 7 days, and 2 patients was achieving complete remission waiting for discharge, with average hospital stay of 25 days. A patient recently admitted to Shifaa ward, experience severe SARS-CoV 2 symptoms.

Salivary, nasal fluid, and phlebotomy blood samples were collected from the patients, a total of 165 samples of serum, saliva and nasal fluid were gathered from the subjects, 55 adult individuals were enrolled to the study, as 40 individuals in the second and first groups (17 male and 23 females, of mean age 41 years, ranging from 17-74 years of age), and 15 individuals were enrolled in the third group (9 female and 6 male, median age of 65 years, ranging from 52 to 81 years).

Double check was made to make sure that first and second group didn't present any symptoms of SARS-COV-2 infection, or had any severe respiratory

symptoms or other illness. The third group was on going SARS-COV-2 illness, presenting a range of symptoms from mild convalescence symptoms to an ARDS, on multiple medication type to support life during the acute stage of illness. The study was presented and gained approval by the medical research ethics department at the college of dentistry university of Mosul. (REC reference no. – UoM.Dent/H.OM.62/ 22).

Investigating the comparative efficacy of mRNA BNT162b2 COVID-19 vaccine Comirnaty (Pfizer/BioNTech, New York, NY, USA), versus placebo, 75 subjects were enrolled to the study, assigned to each of the study groups as 35 subjects to be followed retrospectively by questioning technique for a period of 3 month for any positive cases of COVID-19 and symptomatology of severe COVID-19, and 40 subjects to be randomized to three subgroups and followed prospectively for either single (20 subjects), double (13 subjects) or triple (7 subjects) vaccination doses 21 days apart, see (Table 4-3).

Inclusion and exclusion criteria, for the comparative efficacy of vaccine versus placebo

Subjects from 16 to 75 years old were selected, and based on past medical history all subjects with stable chronic medical disease were included and participants in the experiment could not have had an infection with the hepatitis B, hepatitis C, or Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV).

Prospective follow up study group, all subjects must have a negative COVID-19 history at least 60 days before enrolment to the trial, and must be free from serious medical conditions at time of enrollment to eliminate study outcome bias.

In retrospective follow up group, all subjects must be free from severe debilitating COVID-19 infection, not having a poorly controlled chronic medical condition, and fit to participate in the study, as well as a vaccination negative history prior to enrollment to the study.

Both prospective and retrospective study groups members must not immunocompromised, taking steroids, or any immunosuppressants medication throughout the treatment period.

3.2 Collection of Samples and Data

3.2.a Linked Serology Investigation

All patients were enrolled for blood, nasal secretions, and saliva samples, signed a consent form and patient information sheet were filled to take the full data. (Appendix I).

Nasal secretions were sampled, simply by wrapping a piece of cotton wool around the tip of cotton buds (Massey *Et al.* 2020), see (Figure 3.3), then insert gently into the nasal orifice of subject for five minutes, after removal put into a plastic urine collection container with 15 ml of normal saline 0.9% NaCl solution, then transfer the cotton bud with the wrapped cotton wool around with the surrounding water via syringe, into a disposable plastic PP sampling/freezing tube and then deep freeze in a chest freezer to (-20°C) (Gulec *et al.*, 2021).

The saliva was collected using a dental cotton roll (Kozaki & Hidaka, 2018b), see (Figure 3.3), put and hold in the mouth for a 3 minutes average, simply by pulling the cheek of the subject then insert the cotton roll between the cheek and the gum adjacent to the 6th molar, after removal put into a standard 5 ml syringe, then squeeze the plunger into the barrel of the syringe while the cotton roll is inside,

the squeezed fluid was collected via a disposable plastic PP sampling and freezing tube, then deep freeze into a chest freezer at (-20°C) (Gulec *et al.*, 2021).

Finally, the serum was collected via a peripheral venous blood sampling phlebotomy (Tuck *et al.*, 2009), collected into a serum separating tube (SST) tube with gel and clot activator, then centrifugation for 15 min at 3500 X g, then the serum was stored in same tube at (-20°C) in a chest freezer (Gulec *et al.*, 2021).

Each day, samples were collected in a cool box, the patient's enrollment sheet is prepared a day before going to the hospital, and a plan of sampling is set. Al Salam teaching hospital, sampling was performed in the vaccination center, specifically in the physician examination room prior to administration of vaccine shot.

Enrollment is performed upon questioning first to the participants, to check their infection and medical history, all data were documented in a patient's information sheet. (appendix II).

Patients were instructed to take a rest first in the sampling zone, a nasal cotton piece for sampling, with the dental cotton piece with associated syringe, and an SST tube for blood sampling, is all prepared and numbered according to the sampling plan set earlier. Patients was instructed to place a dental cotton at the side of the cheek then after a minute circulate the cotton gentle with tongue to the other side and place it for a minute then the cotton is drawn and place inside and an open syringe chamber, then squeeze the plunger after replacing it and hardly press the plunger with the cotton inside, the eluted saliva was collected inside the disposable plastic tube with NaCl solution inside (Normal Saline). The patient then given a rest for 5 minutes, then instructed to tilt the head back, and a cotton bud was inserted gently into his nose, after 5 minutes the cotton bud was removed, and placed in the normal saline within the plastic tube, and both placed inside the cool box

immediately. Blood samples were centrifuged immediately after sampling in the adjacent central laboratory in the hospital.

Upon completing the sampling from all site intended, the subject specific samples are placed in a cool box, around which were an ice packs, and closed immediately, in an ordered method to facilitate segmentation upon returning to the laboratory for deep freeze storage. Numbers are closely matching to the numbers of subjects, and patient information sheet accordingly is placed in a documents storing file prepared earlier to facilitate data collection.

Once the sampling target for the specific day is achieved, sterilization and disinfection to the working place is performed.

Upon returning to college laboratory, a chest deep freezer was used to store the samples for later ELISA testing. The chest freezer was placed in isolated area within laboratory, a power supply was provided to ensure continues cooling and deep freezing of samples, to maintain viability, and credibility of testing later. In the laboratory, samples storage is in a small chest freezer of 60 cm * 60 cm * 150 cm dimension.

At Al Shifaa hospital, the cooperative patients were treated the same way the vaccinated and control subjects were treated in Al Salam Hospital, with extra precaution measure on the operator to be taken (PPE and proper care upon handling patients), as in (Figure 3.2).

Critical care patients must be handled with special care and precaution, after wearing the tightly sealed PPE, the subject was approached with caution, and the side cheek was exposed then a piece of cotton was placed at the side, if the mouth was dry due to oxygen continuous flow, then the patient mouth is sprayed with normal saline first, then parotid massage is done to triggered salivation, (Hiraba *et al.*, 2014).

Regarding the nasal fluid samples, it's during the routine nasal sample collection for SARS-CoV-2 qPCR testing, the patient specific nasal swab was taken, then the samples was immediately diluted in the normal saline within the collection PP tube and placed inside the cool box, for storage purpose.

The serum samples were taken from the main laboratory inside the hospital, after proper biochemical tests were performed to the patient. In either hospital, the collection box is a thick cork box, with fitted cork cover, inside which was a tube collection tray surrounded by an ice pack (5 pieces), to maintain cold inside the cork box.

Figure 3.2: - Precaution and equipmentation during sample collection from alshifaa Hospital.

Figure 3.3: Serum, nasal and salivary fluids collection kits.

3.2.b. For the comparative vaccine efficacy versus placebo

Seventy-five members were enrolled to two study groups, first the prospective study group, included 40 subjects subdivided into 20 subjects to take the first vaccination dose then phone numbers were taken and patients full information was taken to ensure meeting the inclusion exclusion criteria, follow up for 3 months following the single dose were performed to document the results and perform the proper analysis. Other 13 subjects were assigned to the two-vaccination dose this time 25 days apart, also followed prospectively to make sure of the results and interpret the outcomes, finally 7 members were enrolled to the three-vaccination group, with 25 days between the doses, all outcomes are closely followed to make an accurate documentation of the results, and clarify the prospective data as a graph.

Thirty-five subjects represented the placebo comparative arm in this trail. 15 subjects were enrolled randomly from COVID-19 quarantine ward at Al Shifaa hospital in Mosul, those were severely debilitated were not enlisted in this randomization. All recruited subjects had a negative vaccination status before enrolment. 20 subjects were enrolled from AlSalam teaching hospital, vaccination ward, prior to taking the first dose of vaccination. In both subgroups a deep questioning technique was performed to clarify the past vaccination, medical, genetic, infectious as well as COVID-19 status in the past 3-month period of the study, to make a clear interpretation of the collected data in hand, to reflect a clear retrospective history of the results.

Following up of cases and documentation in the prospective group was performed by routine communication via a phone number and messages, of any presented reactions, signs and symptoms, and documenting all possible cases of COVID-19 via genomic sequencing of the suspected cases and making the proper

documentation. Follow up of all medication from antipyretics, analgesic to antibiotic use to muscle relaxants.

Following up the retrospective study group, involves the questioning and close probing of the participants for the signs and symptoms of COVID-19 in the past 3 months prior to questioning, as well as positive documented cases of COVID-19 via NAAT or serology, the vaccination status, the medication, the chronic disease status of the participants.

Data set from both groups are gathered and uniformly placed in a statistical chart to facilitate data extraction and interpretation. All cases are strictly investigated to check whether they meet the inclusion or exclusion criteria prior to proceeding with statistical analysis and results.

3.3 ELISA Based Assays for the Linked Serology Study

The test principle is based on class G immunoglobulins (IgG), assay against modified nucleocapsid protein of SARS-CoV-2 (MacMullan *et al.*, 2020), as well as Class A immunoglobulin (IgA) against the receptor binding domain (RBD) recombinant S1 domain of the spike protein of SARS-CoV-2, within the saliva, nasal secretions, and serum body fluids. Assay was performed utilizing ELISA kit on a wells plate, each well is coated with a recombinant nucleocapsid protein antigen from (Euroimmun Medizinische Laboragnostika AG, Luebeck, Germany).

Steps for testing are

- 1- Planning the plate to fix the numbers of samples distribution and operational execution in the laboratory, so as to facilitate data extraction and analysis after obtaining the results.

- 2- Before departing to the laboratory, collecting the samples from the chest freezer into the cool box with ice packs, with the working plan according to point 1, then collecting the proper ELISA kit according to point 1.
- 3- At the Laboratory, thawing of samples is performed in a safe cabin, while thawing the entire samples, a working zone is prepared by placing a tube bar, on the operating table, then numbering of each tube according to preset working plan in point 1.
- 4- Placing the thawed test tubes, in the tube bar according to the plan, then opening the ELISA kit and placing each kit in a specific area of working place, according to the sequence of action in the procedure.
- 5- Remove the cover of testing plate inside the kit, then placing it on a white A4 paper, to reflect the additions, and identify the sequence of additions in steps, by color.
- 6- Based on the kit manufacturer's instructions, the patients' serum sample were first diluted 1:101 μl by the sample buffer solution, saliva and nasal samples were directly pipetted from the collection storage tubes directly into the well of plate as 100 μl for each.
- 7- First operating step, is placement of a standardizing solutions, calibration, positive and negative control in the testing plate wells. The calibration solution, positive and negative controls were plotted then executed according to plot, into the wells of plate as 100 μl in each well from all the mentioned solutions respectively as plotted. Usually, the first three wells are for the standard solution to facilitate calculation, analysis and data interpretation.
- 8- According to the plan of plot, the samples is placed inside each well designated to it, then after completing the additions, then the plate was undergone incubation for 60 minutes at $\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$ of 37°C , in a special samples operating incubator.

- 9- Followed by a washing procedure of three washing cycles using 300 μ l of working-strength buffer solution, within the kit. Then the wells were dried for 10 minutes.
- 10- The next step is adding the enzyme conjugate as 100 μ l each dried well, (peroxidase-labelled antihuman IgG as well as IgA) according to analysis performed in each run, then incubation is followed for 30 minutes at $37^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$.
- 11- A washing of three washing cycles using the same wash solution was done for each well, then drying for 10 minutes.
- 12- Then an addition of 100 μ l of chromogenic/ substrate solution was done (TMB/H₂O₂), to each of the dried well, then a slight color developed by the chemical reaction, this color was eventually developed totally by incubation for 15 minutes $37^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$.
- 13- eventually a 100 μ l of a stop solution (0.5 M sulphuric acid is added, an immediate color fixation was achieved.
- 14- The absorbance testing of plates was performed utilizing a ChroMate 4300, PC-controlled ELISA 8-channel microplate reader, at operating wavelength of 450 nm, as stated by manufacturer of test kit, it measures Absorbance of 96 wells in approximately 12 seconds, it`s a software compatible with Microsoft® Windows® (Engvall 2010). See (Figure 3.4).
- 15- In each test well the absorbance reading was directly proportional to the amount of immunoglobulin present, and the extent of associated colorimetric reaction.
- 16- The results were calculated depending on the test kit design, that reflects a semi quantitative indicator of concentration, measuring a ratio of extinction of control or patients' samples over the extinction of the calibrator, by taking a

ratio of the samples A° reading value to the Calibrator A° reading value. (Thiha, Ibrahim 2015).

The manufacturer recommends that a ratio results of < 0.8 is to be considered negative, and a ratio of ≥ 0.8 to < 1.1 is a borderline, and a ratio result of ≥ 1.1 is considered positive. (appendix III).

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Figure 3.4: ChroMate 4300, PC-controlled ELISA 8-channel microplate reader.
Adapted from: (Index of /Wp-content/Uploads/2019/08, n.d.)

3.4 Data Analysis and Statistics

Statistics are run for both investigations made as follow:

1- For the linked serology assay study

Statistics and analytical investigations of results, and graphs, figures and tables were performed with SPSS version 24 (Arkkelin, n.d., 2014), as well as Microsoft excel version (16.0.15028), test equations were performed via Mann-Whitney U Test, as well as The Kruskal-Wallis H test, to evaluate the non-gaussian distribution among the study group, of non-parametric testing scheme. The categorical data were presented as numbers and/or percentages and continuous data as median and range. For each of the outcomes, $p < 0.05$ was undertaken as statistically significant.

2- For the comparative vaccine efficacy study

Charting of the extracted data is performed via Microsoft Excel V-16.0, the number of cases per month were placed according to timeline per days of the intended study period of 3 months as 10 days gap of collection of outcomes.

The percentage of case incidence from the total number of subjects in the given group was performed for each time period, then the cumulative incidence over the entire period was taken by sum of the percentage incidence over all periods until the end of the proposed time of the study of 3 months. The comparative statistics between the two main study groups was performed via the Relative risk ratio analysis (RRR), between the cumulative percentage of incidence of COVID-19 cases in prospective vaccination groups in total and the corresponding retrospective study of placebo control.

The vaccination efficacy was measure as the percentile gab of RRR between the two study groups. Cumulative percent of adverse effects was also measured for both groups, and RRR was then found to reflect significance of outcome, tracking the vaccine induced post injection adverse events and timing the of occurrence can add cumulative knowledge of the safety, tolerance and overall profile of adverse events associated with COVID-19 vaccination.

Chapter Four

Results and Discussion

4.a- General Review of Patient’s Population Enlisted to study

Linked serology assay participants were enrolled to three study groups (Table 4.1), more details for study group enrollment in (Table 4.2).

Table 4.1: General review of patient’s population enlisted to linked serology investigations.

Study groups	Vaccination status	History SARS-CoV-2 infection
1 st Vaccinated group T α (n = 20)	Subjects enrolled after returning for the 2nd mRNA BNT126b2b vaccination	They have had no past SARS-COV-2 infections.
2 nd Healthy group T β (n = 20)	Those Non-vaccinated subjects, recruited Just before the 1 st dose of mRNA BNT126b2b vaccination	They have had no past SARS-COV-2 infection.
COVID- 19 group T γ (n = 15)	Non-vaccinated	Ongoing SARS-COV-2 infection or recently recovering from the severe symptom stage

Table 4.2: Specific data of patient’s population enlisted to linked serology investigations.

	Al Salam Hospital	AlShifaa Hospital
Numbers of patients	40 patients	15 patients
Gender	23 females	9 females
	17 males	6 males
Status	7 attending to third booster dose of Vaccination	11 were in Shifaa section mild to moderate intensity status
	13 attending to second booster dose of Vaccination	4 were in Shifaa section severe ARDS status
	20 attending to first booster dose of Vaccination	
Age Range (Years)	17 – 74 years	52 – 81 years
Date of sampling	9/February/2022	16/February/2022
	To 15/February/2022	To 26/February/2022
Site of sampling	Vaccination center	Shifaa Quarantine ward
	Al Salam Consultancy ward	Shifaa intensive care Ward
Duration of sampling	6 days	9 days

For the purpose of investigating the comparative efficacy of mRNA BNT162b2 COVID-19 vaccine Comirnaty (Pfizer/BioNTech, New York, NY, USA), versus placebo, 75 subjects were enrolled to the study, (Table 4.3).

Table 4.3: General review of patient’s population enlisted to study for the comparative vaccine efficacy study.

Study groups	Vaccination status	Cumulative positive cases
1st Vaccinated group Tα (n = 40)	Subjects enrolled while attending to the mRNA BNT126b2b vaccination.	6 cases were confirmed from 3 month prospective follow up
	7 subjects were taking the third booster shot	0 from third booster group
	13 persons were taking the second booster dose	1 from the second booster group
	20 persons were taking the first vaccination dose	5 from the first vaccination shot
2nd Placebo Tβ (n = 35)	20 persons were taking prior to the first vaccination dose, retrospectively investigated by questionnaire method, excluded from the 20 subjects included in linked serology study.	21 cases were confirmed from 3-month retrospective investigation
	15 COVID-19 positive cases not vaccinated before enrollment from quarantine hospital and retrospectively investigated by questionnaire method	6 from vaccination 1 st dose group, past medical history. 15 from the quarantine hospital group

4.b- Results for the linked serological assay study,

Immunoglobulins against SARS-COV-2, IgG-NCP and IgA-S1 RBD was investigated in the serum, saliva and nasal fluids of 20 control of healthy state, 20 vaccinated individuals, and 15 convalescent individuals from SARS-COV-2 infection. In the final study group of 15 individuals, 4 were on severe symptoms and in RCU unit on artificial ventilator devices, and 11 were fully recovered from symptoms.

Considering that a reliable testing for Anti SARS-COV-2 immunoglobulins in saliva and nasal fluids is not commercially and clinically available, the procedure made the

serum-based kits approach compatible with the results from the groups, to reflect a homogeneous result among the three different groups.

Using the ratio between the sample and calibrator A° , the findings were semi-quantitatively determined. According to the manufacturer, the serum cut-offs were deemed negative for all values < 0.8 COI (cut-off index), ambiguous for all values between 0.8 and 1.1 COI, and positive for all values > 1.1 COI.

Discussion For the Linked Serological Assay Study,

Regarding the median serum Immunoglobulins levels, it was found that both IgA-RBD and IgG-NCP are statistically more significant compared with the control median levels, (in the Convalescent IgA; 2.51 COI for A° , IgG; 5 COI for A° , and in the vaccinated (IgA; 3 COI for A° , IgG; 2.515 COI for A°) as compared to the control group IgA; 0.59 COI for A° , IgG 0.3 COI for A°) that's why COVID-19 vaccine efficacy follow up and COVID-19 infection status and extent of natural immunity can be checked via these two parameters in this fluid sample.

Heterogenic presentations in term of symptoms severity, immunological response, and infection susceptibility, is the notable characteristics of Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19). Accordingly, its essential to understand these variations among individuals to reflect on significant interventions, in term of individualized escalation of medical care, as well as customized medical interventions, most important of all is the applicability of vaccination (Benetti *et al.*, 2020).

A valid indicator of the vaccination induced immunization, are a seriously developing urgency of interest for both practical and theoretical goals. Protection against any infection upon future attacks defends to great extent on the development of a distinct antibodies, following the administration of nearly all the type of vaccines invented to date. In order to effectively block the infection and truly protect

against infections, these antibodies must be situated to a higher concentration at the mucosa of the portals of entry, according to the established fact by Plotkin (Plotkin 2010). Nasal and salivary immunity against SARS-CoV-2, to the date still not sufficiently documented and vaccine triggered humoral-mucosal immunity, still few research documented about and more work is needed to investigate. Following acute attack of SARS, it was shown that distinct immune response in the form of IgA is measurable in the Saliva (Wang et al., 2021, Varadhachary *et al.*, 2020, Aita *et al.*, 2020), persist for nearly 3 months following the infection (Chansaenroj *et al.*, 2022). One article, (Ketas *et al.*, 2021), pointed out that initial evidence of salivary anti-SARS-COV-2 monoclonal antibodies of IgA type, are detectable following a routine test examination of a vaccinated healthcare practitioners. Some others, suggested that even in the absence of mucosal IgA as said triggered by COVID-19 vaccine administration, still a chance of inflammation induced memory B cells translocation that elaborates IgA to the mucosal sites (Ketas *et al.*, 2021, Mortari *et al.*, 2021).

In recent findings, (Fröberg *et al.*, 2021), suggested that huge amount of nasal fluid derived IgA is detectable upon acute attack of COVID-19 infection, that has a serum and saliva like kinetics of serology. Still, vaccine triggered nasal immunity have not been thoroughly studied and quantified, the usual standard technique for monoclonal antibody quantification in the salivary and nasal fluids samples need a further clarification. In the current study it was found that the mRNA BNT162b2 COVID-19 vaccine Comirnaty (Pfizer/ BioNTech, New York, NY, USA), will trigger developing both mucosal and circulatory selective IgG and IgA monoclonal antibodies, specific toward the nucleocapsid protein and the S1-RBD receptor binding protein of SARS, respectively. In vaccinated subjects, secretory antibodies directed against SARS-COV-2 becomes detectable in nasal and salivary fluid, those have not been previously infected with natural infection, this is an

unusual finding, and present interesting evidence, so to allow to postulates that vaccination can provide a protective barrier against infections, at the site of viral ingress to the body. If a comparative analysis of vaccine vs naturally acquired humoral immune response was made, it would help to better make sense of how effective and true potential of COVID-19 vaccinations is. Since few studies are validated enough to reflect saliva and nasal fluids data of this immunoglobulin's levels in these conditions, our study indicated that our pre-analysis and post analysis procedures and associated findings, are consistent. In this study, all control healthy subjects presented with a nearly non-detectable Anti-SARS-COV-2 IgA S1 RBD and IgG NCP, it was significantly low as compared to vaccinated individuals and COVID-19 individuals. In this study all subjects vaccinated and convalescent subjects presented with significantly higher anti-SARS-COV-2 IgA S1 RBD and IgG NCP, as compared to control healthy subjects, in both vaccinated and convalescent groups. If we consider the fact that vaccinated individuals are of the same status as that of control healthy groups, with vaccinations is the newly introduced variable, the data from this individual reflects that IgA S1 RBD as well as IgG NCP levels increases in response to vaccination.

4.b.1 Comparative serological investigations result per samples type

4.b.1.1 Investigation of Anti-SARS-CoV-2 antibodies in Serum Samples

Considering (Table 4.4 and Table 4.5, Figure 4.1), the median and range values of COI for A° of the serum concentration of Anti SARS-CoV-2 IgA-S1 RBD and Anti SARS-CoV-2 IgG-NCP, the values were notably higher in the Convalescent (IgA; 2.51 COI for A°, IgG; 5 COI for A°), and in the vaccinated (IgA; 3 COI for A°, IgG; 2.515 COI for A°) as compared to the control group (IgA; 0.59 COI for A°, IgG 0.3 COI for A°), in both IgA and IgG group.

Statistical point of view, data in the IgA-S1 RBD as well as IgG-NCP, were statistically significant $p < 0.0001$ between the control healthy individuals vs. the convalescent population, and among the vaccinated subjects and the control healthy group $p < 0.0001$. within the IgG-NCP group the data were statistically significant between the Convalescent and the Vaccinated groups, with a p-value of $p < 0.0001$, in the IgA-S1 RBD group the data statistically non-significant with a p-value of $p < 0.33$, we take the value of $p < 0.05$ as an indicator of statistical significance.

Table 4.4: Median, Range and Mann Whitney test result, and significance test outcome for each of the study groups in the Serum IgG NCP population, with comparative statistics.

Test type	Study group	Median	Range	Mann Whitney	Sig,
IgG-NCP	vaccinated	2.515 COI for A ^o	(1.12 – 7.82)	45.000 *	0.0001
	Convalescent	5 COI for A ^o	(2.72 – 6.84)		
	Control	0.3 COI for A ^o	(0.21 – 0.26)	0.000 *	0.0001
	vaccinated	2.515 COI for A ^o	(1.12 – 7.82)	0.000 *	0.0001
	Control	0.3 COI for A ^o	(0.21 – 0.26)		
	Convalescent	5 COI for A ^o	(2.72 – 6.84)		

Table 4.5: Median, Range and Mann Whitney test result, and significance test outcome for each of the study groups in the Serum IgA RBD population, with comparative statistics.

test type	Study group	Median	Range	Mann Whitney	Sig,
IgA-RBD	vaccinated	3 COI for A ^o	(1.26-5.27)	120.500	0.33
	Convalescent	2.51 COI for A ^o	(1.12 - 4.5)		
	Control	0.59 COI for A ^o	(0.28-0.95)	0.000 *	0.0001
	vaccinated	3 COI for A ^o	(1.26-5.27)	0.000 *	0.0001
	Control	0.59 COI for A ^o	(0.28-0.95)		
	Convalescent	2.51 COI for A ^o	(1.12 - 4.5)		

Figure 4.1: Serum-based samples level of Anti SARS-CoV 2 IgG-NCP and Anti SARS-CoV 2 IgA-RBD. (a) median levels of Anti SARS CoV2 IgA-S1 RBD in term of ratio from the test calibrator in the three comparative groups. (b) Median levels of Anti SARS CoV 2 IgG-NCP in terms of ratio from the test calibrator in the three comparative groups.

Discussion involves Serum Samples Serological Antibody Assay:

Notable of concern, that serum IgG of convalescent subjects had a mean value higher compared to vaccinated IgG mean value, both were significantly higher than mean value of control healthy group. This gives indication that COVID-19 infection gives a stronger more robust antigen challenge that reflects a higher immune response (Karachaliou *et al.*, 2022). Data from (Alharbi *et al.*, 2022) suggested that vaccine induced IgG humoral antibody response, tends to wane after 6 months up to 1 year post priming dose, yet gives robust antibody response and blood titers. (Hall *et al.*, 2022), discovered that the level of protection provided by an infection remained high for up to a year before starting to decline. It's notably interesting that participants in research (Kojima *et al.*, 2021) who recovered from a

moderate COVID infection were shown to have robust high titers, long-lasting antigen-specific immunity. Although studies have shown that protection against reinfection is effective, of considerably high titer levels post natural infection and may extend for more than 10 months, the precise length of the protective immunity is unknown (Kojima *et al.*, 2021). From this stand point our result in this work came exactly reflecting the proposed facts in past researches.

Antigen challenge to trigger IgA response is comparative in Convalescent and vaccinated groups of serum samples, both are statistically significant over control healthy groups. This gives strong evidence that vaccination can develop a robust protective immunity in the serum, and from which a selective S-IgA secreting mucosal cells as well as salivary gland resident plasma cells would elaborate S-IgA at the portals of entry of the virus, the saliva of oral cavity, the nasal mucosa, as well as the mucosa of the upper respiratory tract. Facts that COVID-19 infection can trigger a robust IgA serum response is reported by (Ma et al, 2020), how reported a significantly high serum levels of IgA post infection in qPCR positive cases 15 days post symptomatic phase and persist for a long time. A relatively high serum and mucosal IgA antibody response is reported by (Sheikh-Mohamed *Et al.*2022), they claimed that high anti-Spike/RBD serum IgA levels are linked with protection against subsequent breakthrough infection and that anti-Spike sIgA are elicited and retained in the saliva of around 30% of mRNA vaccinated subjects. It has been shown that intranasal (I.N.) adenoviral-based vaccinations that strongly produce anti-Spike/RBD IgA may stop transmission in golden hamsters. Furthermore, compared to I.M. alone regimens, a SARS-CoV-2 mRNA vaccine I.M. prime followed by an adenoviral I.N. boost offers greater protection against infection, especially against divergent versions like B.1.1.351 (beta). their findings imply that an I.M. prime followed by I.N. boost approach is worthwhile taking into

account for both wide protection against developing variants and avoiding person-to-person transmission of SARS-CoV-2. Our results came closely resembling the current available data on this topic presented by authors on this topic.

4.b.1.2 Investigation of Anti-SARS-CoV-2 antibodies in Saliva Samples

Salivary concentration of Anti SARS-COV-2 IgA-S1 RBD and IgG NCP, In the saliva samples, the median anti-SARS-CoV-2 IgA concentrations were higher in vaccinated and convalescent groups compared to control healthy subjects, median values were slightly higher for IgA-RBD in the convalescent as compared to vaccinated group (IgA-RBD Vaccinated 2.41 COI for A^o; IgA-RBD convalescent 2.48 COI for A^o), and both was by far higher than control healthy group (IgA-RBD 0.67 COI for A^o). IgG-NCP median values were relatively higher for the convalescent vs the vaccinated subject group, (IgG-NCP convalescent 2.1 COI for A^o; IgG-NCP vaccinated 1.69 COI for A^o) both were by far higher than median value for control healthy group, (IgG-NCP 0.625 COI for A^o), (Table 4.6 and 4.7, and Figure 4.2) reflects the numerical data.

Median data set were statistically significant if we compare Convalescent and/or vaccinated subjects' median values to that of control healthy subjects' group median value, both with $P < 0.0001$, data were statistically non-significantly different between the vaccinated and convalescent groups median values, with a $p < 0.069$ in term of IgG-NCP as well as the value of $p < 0.419$ in term of IgA S1-RBD, again we take the value of $p < 0.05$ as an indicator of statistical significance.

Table 4.6: Median, Range and Mann Whitney test result, and significance test outcome for each of the study groups in the Salivary IgG NCP population, with comparative statistics.

Test type	Study group	Median	Range	Mann Whitney	Sig,
IgG-NCP	vaccinated	1.69 COI for A ^o	(1.22 – 5.36)	95.000	0.069
	Convalescent	2.1 COI for A ^o	(1.46 – 2.7)		
	Control	0.625 COI for A ^o	(0.26 – 0.98)	0.000 **	0.0001
	vaccinated	1.69 COI for A ^o	(1.22 – 5.36)		
	Control	0.625 COI for A ^o	(0.26 – 0.98)		
	Convalescent	2.1 COI for A ^o	(1.46 – 2.7)		

Table 4.7: Median, Range and Mann Whitney test result, and significance test outcome for each of the study groups in the Salivary IgA RBD population, with comparative statistics.

test type	Study group	median	range	Mann Whitney	Sig,
IgA-RBD	Vaccinated	2.41 COI for A ^o	(1.22 – 5.36)	125.50	0.419
	Convalescent	2.48 COI for A ^o	(1.46 – 2.7)		
	Control	0.67 COI for A ^o	(0.26 – 0.98)	0.000 *	0.0001
	vaccinated	2.41 COI for A ^o	(1.22 – 5.36)		
	Control	0.67 COI for A ^o	(0.26 – 0.98)		
	Convalescent	2.48 COI for A ^o	(1.46 – 2.7)		

Figure 4.2: Saliva based samples level of Anti SARS-CoV 2 IgG-NCP and Anti SARS-CoV 2 IgA-RBD. (a) median levels of Anti SARS CoV2 IgA-S1 RBD in term of ratio from the test calibrator in the three comparative groups. (b) Median levels of Anti SARS CoV 2 IgG-NCP in terms of ratio from the test calibrator in the three comparative groups.

Discussion involves Saliva Samples Serological Antibody Assay:

The salivary Immunoglobulins pattern is somewhat interesting. Salivary IgG mean value in convalescent members is still higher than vaccinated subjects mean value (Fröberg *et al.*, 2021, Zhang *et al.*, 2020), both are statistically more significant than control healthy subjects mean value. Salivary IgA gives a typical higher mean value compared to control healthy groups, and to extend the observation, a higher value compared to salivary IgG groups, this result correlates with a published fact by (Zhang *et al.*, 2022), that a key element of mucosal immunity is secretory IgA, which is clearly detectable in saliva. IgA has been shown to be the predominant antibody in the early humoral response to SARS-CoV-2. Younger people with moderate SARS-CoV-2 infections were observed to have higher prevalence of salivary IgA antibody responses. The amount and detection rate

of IgA in saliva were also greater than those of IgG and IgM, according to our research. IgA, IgG, and IgM levels in matched saliva and blood samples were all substantially associated, according to the examination of saliva and serum SARS-CoV-2-specific antibodies. However, the connection between IgA levels in the saliva and IgA levels in the serum was the weakest.

If we consider our results again, in case of salivary IgA post vaccination provide a relatively high though non-statistically significant mean value, but notably a higher mean value than does convalescent subjects mean value. This coincides with the above serum values observation of IgA immunoglobulins, establish the protective role of vaccination at the viral portals of entry, to prevent future attacks of infections (Chi *et al.*, 2022), (Darwich *et al.*, 2022) demonstrated how the BNT162b2 vaccination enables the release of salivary SARS-CoV-2-specific Igs. Saliva antibodies most likely come from the serum since they are derived from the microvasculature of gingival fissures. While IgA (present in the plasma as the protease-susceptible IgA1 isotype) are present at extremely low levels, IgG are more stable and progressively grow with time. Additionally, we demonstrate that at three months, SARS-CoV-2-specific Ig in both the plasma and saliva have almost entirely disappeared.

4.b.1.3 investigation of Anti-SARS-CoV-2 antibodies in Nasal Fluid Samples

Concentration of Anti SARS-COV-2 IgA-S1 RBD and IgG NCP, In the nasal secretion samples, had a higher median value of anti-SARS-CoV-2 IgA concentrations in vaccinated and convalescent groups compared to control healthy subjects, median values were relatively higher for IgA-RBD in the convalescent as compared to vaccinated group (IgA-RBD convalescent 1.94 COI for A°; IgA-RBD Vaccinated 1.84 COI for A°), and both was by far higher than control healthy group

(IgA-RBD 0.71 COI for A^o). IgG-NCP median values were slightly lower for the convalescent vs the vaccinated subject group, (IgG-NCP convalescent 1.47 COI for A^o; IgG-NCP vaccinated 1.52 COI for A^o) both were by far higher than median value for control healthy group, (IgG-NCP 0.34 COI for A^o), (Table 4.8 and 4.9, Figure 4.3) reflects the numerical data.

Median data set were statistically significant if we compare Convalescent and/or vaccinated groups median values to that of control group median value, both with ($P < 0.0001$), data were statistically non-significantly different between the vaccinated and convalescent groups median values, with a ($p < 0.521$) in term of IgG-NCP as well as the value of ($p < 0.6810$) in term of IgA S1-RBD, again we take the value of $p < 0.05$ as an indicator of statistical significance.

Table 4.8: Median, Range and Mann Whitney test result, and significance test outcome for each of the study groups in the nasal fluid IgA RBD population, with comparative statistics.

test type	Study group	median	range	Mann Whitney	Sig,
IgA-RBD	vaccinated	1.84 COI for A ^o	(1.1 – 2.95)	130.5	0.521
	Convalescent	1.94 COI for A ^o	(1.07 – 2.7)		
	Control	0.71 COI for A ^o	(0.34 – 1)	0.000 *	0.0001
	vaccinated	1.84 COI for A ^o	(1.1 – 2.95)		
	Control	0.71 COI for A ^o	(0.34 – 1)	0.000 *	0.0001
	Convalescent	1.94 COI for A ^o	(1.07 – 2.7)		

Table 4.9: Median, Range and Mann Whitney test result, and significance test outcome for each of the study groups in the Nasal IgG NCP population, with comparative statistics.

test type	Study group	median	range	Mann Whitney	Sig,
IgG-NCP	vaccinated	1.52 COI for A ^o	(1.02 – 6.28)	130.5	0.521
	Convalescent	1.47 COI for A ^o	(1.36 – 5.56)		
	Control	0.34 COI for A ^o	(0.13 – 0.93)	0.000 *	0.0001
	vaccinated	1.52 COI for A ^o	(1.02 – 6.28)		
	Control	0.34 COI for A ^o	(0.13 – 0.93)	0.000 *	0.0001
	Convalescent	1.47 COI for A ^o	(1.36 – 5.56)		

Figure 4.3: Nasal fluid based samples level of Anti SARS-CoV 2 IgG-NCP and Anti SARS-CoV 2 IgA-RBD. (a) median levels of Anti SARS CoV2 IgA-S1 RBD in term of ratio from the test calibrator in the three comparative groups. (b) Median levels of Anti SARS CoV 2 IgG-NCP in terms of ratio from the test calibrator in the three comparative groups.

Discussion involves Nasal Fluid Samples Serological Antibody Assay:

Nasal fluid IgG levels in both groups, convalescent and vaccinated means values are nearly equivalent in values and non-statistically significant difference where found. Both were statistically significant over the mean of the control group. In (Fröberg *et al.*, 2021) investigation, they demonstrated that an early and stronger nasal antibody response may be crucial in reducing illness by starting early viral clearance and making systemic symptoms easier to treat. To confirm the function of nasal antibodies in clinical protection, further study is required. Nasal IgA and IgG antibodies are still detected nine months after infection and probably provide some protection from re-infection. Monitoring post-infection and post-vaccination nasal antibody levels may help us to spot early indications of the diminishing immunity

against infection since mucosal antibodies are the first line of defense against viral infection. Finally, the study design and analytic approach described here might serve as a model for further research into COVID-19 and other viral disorders.

Convalescent group IgA median values were slightly higher yet statistically non-significant in term of difference in median values compared to vaccinated group; both are higher in median value than control healthy group. Nasal Immunoglobulins are a novel concept of humoral immunity study in a distinct anatomical compartment, and from protective point of view (Joseph, 2022b).

The presented fact earlier that a non-replicating vaccine given via parenteral route would not induce a mucosal tissue associated immune response (Neutra & Kozlowski, 2006). Currently, data from experimental and clinical investigations have brought this theory into a challenge (Lapiente *et al.*, 2021). An astonishing and theoretical shifting finding is the detection of salivary and nasal fluid anti-SARS-COV-2 IgA antibody, after routine systemic vaccination, with no previous infection status reported for these subjects. In our study we established the fact that systemic vaccination can hamper protection against future attacks, by provision of mucosal immunity to the site of viral entry to the body.

By investigating saliva of vaccinated individuals with a high selection criterion of no past infection history, we established the fact that salivary IgA is triggered following SARS-COV-2 vaccination via intramuscular mRNA BNT162b2 COVID-19 vaccine, this perfectly coincides with (Ketas *et al.*, 2021), findings still investigating the nasal fluid for humoral immunoglobins is the novel concept of our study. Our study is among the first articles investigating and reports a vaccine medicated SARS-COV-2 nasal immunity and immunoglobulins detection. Our investigation didn't only enroll about IgA RBD detection, in the nasal fluid samples, as it's considered the main class of immunoglobulins in the mucosal area, but we

extended our investigation to anti-SARS-COV-2 IgG NCP within the nasal fluid of the vaccinated group members.

We can explain the fact to the blood exudation during the capillary rupture following cytokine storm (Ibiang *et al.*, 2022), it may also be explained to specific action of the spike cell surface protein on permeability of the capillaries. The two main antibody classes in saliva, sIgA and IgG, are continually influencing oral bacteria and aerodigestive antigens. The latter is exported through an epithelial receptor-mediated mechanism after being produced as pIgA by PCs in salivary glands. Although a little portion may come from glandular, gingival, or tonsillar PCs, most IgG seen in saliva represents systemic immunity since it is obtained from serum by passive diffusion, primarily via gingival crevices. In addition to the paracellular leakage of monomeric IgA and IgG antibodies, individuals with ulcerative colitis will also exhibit additional serum-derived or locally generated components and mediators, such as IL-6, in their entire saliva (Brandtzaeg, 2013).

Further investigations are needed to unveil the true mechanism behind this finding. Investigations aiming for serological testing of vaccinated subjects with COVID-19 vaccines, can be of significant advantage in term of getting to understand the non-vaccinated previously infected subject`s baseline seroprevalence, getting to check the weak or non-responsive to COVID-19 vaccination, calculation of accurate time-based decay of anti-SARS-COV-2 antibodies triggered by vaccination, all was investigated by Lippi *et al.*, (Šošić *Et al.*2021). Among the critical drawbacks of this investigations, is the huge amount of blood sampling and the excess laboratory work demands required to proceed in supporting the continuous flow of data regarding anti-SARS-COV-2 antibody testing serology (SARS-CoV-2 Serology Tests: 3 Big Limitations Doctors Must Understand, 2020).

4.b.2 Comparison of the Serum Immunoglobulins in Different Body Fluids Collectively among the different study groups

If we consider another design for the results assessments, we would put the result for each of the study groups in term of comparative median concentration in each of the study body fluid samples, a Kruskal-Wallis H test gives an indicator of significance between the median concentrations in the study groups.

Table 4.10: comparison of immunoglobulin G (IgG) concentration between the different study groups in different body fluids.

Type of Immunoglobulin	Study Group	Specimen		
		Saliva	Serum	Nasal
IgG-NCP	KS Value	38.87 **	42.51 **	37.68 **
	Sig.	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
	Vaccinated	1.69 COI for A ^o	2.515 COI for A ^o	1.52 COI for A ^o
	Control	0.625 COI for A ^o	0.3 COI for A ^o	0.34 COI for A ^o
	Convalescent	2.1 COI for A ^o	5 COI for A ^o	1.47 COI for A ^o

According to (Table 4.10), vaccinated subjects present a statistically significant difference between the Serum, Saliva, and nasal fluid median concentrations of IgG-NCP levels, in terms of Kruskal-Wallis H test results. Same results can be reflected on the convalescent and control healthy groups, in term of median concentration of IgG-NCP levels, in all the data set results the p value was < 0.0001, results can be interpreted, that our investigation came accurate in term of results, that in the saliva of both the convalescent as well as vaccinated groups was higher in term of median concentration and as compared to control healthy group, it was statistically significant, and that saliva can be utilized as a sampling specimen when first diagnose as well as when following up the patients with active SARS-COV-2 infection, or to check the efficacy and responsiveness to the vaccination. Nasal fluid sample gave a future promise to all airborne viral infection serological

immunity to become detectable just by measuring this fluid instead of serum, and potential kits could be designed to measure this fluid, to become commercially available and applicable.

Table 4.11: comparison of immunoglobulin A (IgA) concentration between the different study groups in different body fluids.

Type of Immunoglobulin	Study Group	Specimen		
		Saliva	Serum	Nasal
IgA-S1 RBD	KS Value	37.78 **	37.89 **	37.59 **
	Sig.	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
	Vaccinated	2.41 COI for A ^o	3 COI for A ^o	1.84 COI for A ^o
	Control	0.67 COI for A ^o	0.59 COI for A ^o	0.71 COI for A ^o
	Convalescent	2.48 COI for A ^o	2.51 COI for A ^o	1.94 COI for A ^o

If we consider (Table 4.11), comparing the median concentration value of IgA-S1 RBD among the three study groups in their different fluid samples, serum, nasal fluid, and saliva, were statistically significant difference in terms of Kruskal-Wallis H test results, all the values were < 0.0001. Same applications and conclusions can be applied to IgA-S1 RBD results, in term of significance and clinical applications in future as that of IgG-NCP.

4.b.3 Comparison Between the Monoclonal Immunoglobulins in Different Body Fluids Individually among the Different Study Groups

If we now consider a head-to-head comparison between the two immunoglobulins, we would focus on the median values of each immunoglobulin in the three-study group in each body fluid individually. Mann Whitney H test is best fit to reflect the statistical significance among the different set of study median values.

4.b.3.1. Comparison between the Immunoglobulins in the Saliva of the Different Study Groups

In saliva results from Mann Whitney test, indicated that vaccinated group's IgA S1-RBD readings is statistically more significant than IgG-NCP, likewise we might consider IgA S1-RBD testing in the Saliva to follow up the efficacy and responsiveness to the vaccination.

In term of Convalescents saliva reading, there is no statistical difference between IgA S1-RBD and IgG-NCP, in term of mean values, by the Mann Whitney H test results of significance, either of which to choose is inevitable, but if we refer to (Table 4.12), we would notice that statistical significance of results between the convalescent vs. Control healthy groups is greater in IgA than does in IgG, as compared to control.

Saliva is a potential for non-invasive techniques to prevent harm and present a sharp data to reflect vaccination status as well as follow up the convalescent subject's immunization status, many articles suggested saliva as a promising diagnostic fluid alternative to serum, for the diagnostic routines in clinical practice.

Table 4.12: comparison between the IgA and IgG between the different study groups in saliva.

Study Group	Mann–Whitney <i>U</i> test	Sig.	IgG	IgA
Vaccinated	84.00 **	0.008	1.69 COI for A ^o	2.41 COI for A ^o
Control	150.50	0.557	0.625 COI for A ^o	0.67 COI for A ^o
Convalescent	105.00	0.775	2.1 COI for A ^o	2.48 COI for A ^o

Discussion involves comparing Immunoglobulins in the Saliva of the different study groups:

Results from (Sheikh-Mohamed *et al.*, 2022) are in line with prior studies indicating that anti-Spike and anti-RBD IgG and IgA may be found in saliva after two doses of BNT162b2 or mRNA-1273, but infection, or a combination of infection plus immunization, causes more robust, and durable, antigen-specific IgA. This work also coincides with the findings above, that we can think about IgA S1-RBD testing in the saliva to follow up on the effectiveness and response to the vaccine as it is statistically more significant for the vaccinated group's IgA S1-RBD readings than IgG-NCP.

There is no statistically significant difference between IgA S1-RBD and IgG-NCP in terms of mean values for convalescents, according to the results of the Mann Whitney H test. However, if we look at (Table 4.6, table 4.7), we can see that the statistical significance of the results between the convalescent vs. control healthy groups is higher in IgA than it is in IgG, as compared to control.

This finding also coincides with (Sheikh-Mohamed *et al.*, 2022), in that higher IgA values, due to the fact that plasma-associated Spike antigen might enter the capillary-encircled salivary glands, triggering a local S-IgA response. Another option is that the gut is the site of a mucosal IgA response to mRNA vaccination, and that plasma cells produced there depart the gut, and spread to other mucosal surfaces like the oral cavity. In fact, after systemic injection of the cholera toxin and yellow fever vaccinations in humans, circulating immune cells have been shown to exhibit the gut homing integrin. The prolonged levels of anti-Spike sIgA in the saliva at 6 months post-boost, which are not seen for the systemic IgG response, may be due to recirculation between mucosal compartments. The best way to get more understanding of the processes behind how SARS-CoV-2 mRNA vaccines induce antigen-specific sIgA synthesis at mucosal surfaces is via the use of animal models.

4.b.3.2. Comparison between the Immunoglobulins in the Serum of the Different Study Groups

In term of serum samples, convalescents IgG-NCP was statistically more significant than does IgA S1-RBD median values readings, this coincides with the established fact that IgG-NCP is best measured in the serum to reflect accurate clinical results.

Regarding control groups this data and median values are in the negative levels; this is even having no values in term of statistical significance readings.

This result pushes us to strongly recommend serum as the ideal test to follow up immunization status as well as the clinical progression following infection, see (Table 4.13).

Table 4.13: comparison between the IgA and IgG between the different study groups in serum

Study Group	Mann–Whitney <i>U</i> test	Sig.	IgG	IgA
Vaccinated	169.50	0.988	2.515 COI for A°	3 COI for A°
Control	67.00 **	0.001	0.3 COI for A°	0.59 COI for A°
Convalescent	22.00 **	0.0001	5 COI for A°	2.51 COI for A°

Discussion involves comparing Immunoglobulins in the serum of the different study groups:

Work by (Glück *et al.*, 2021), reflected the fact that IgM- and IgA-antibody levels specific for SARS-CoV-2 decayed quickly over time, but IgG-antibody levels did so more gradually. Booster immunization caused significantly high IgG- and to a lesser extent IgA-antibodies in those with a history of COVID-19. After receiving a booster vaccine compared to after recovering from COVID-19, antibody levels were significantly greater. When vaccinated on a two-dose regimen, healthy control participants exhibited antibody levels that were comparable to those of those who had previously received COVID-19 and a booster shot. IgA-RBD immunity in serum seems to become more persistent after booster doses, although kinetics of decay would eventually be faster than IgG. Memory T cell numbers for SARS-CoV-2 did not correlate with antibody levels. Nobody who took part in the trial had a reinfection.

In our work, Convalescents' IgG-NCP was statistically more significant in terms of serum samples than were IgA S1-RBD mean value readings; this is consistent with the known fact that IgG-NCP is more accurately evaluated in serum to represent correct clinical outcomes. This data and mean values for the control

groups are in the negative range, and there are even no values in the statistical significance readings. In the case of vaccinated individuals without a prior history of infection with COVID-19, serum IgG-NCP is the ideal test to monitor immunization status as well as the clinical course of infection. Serum IgA-RBD, however, may also be an effective follow-up method because there is no statistically significant difference between the mean values of the two groups.

4.b.3.3 Comparison between the Immunoglobulins in the Nasal Fluid of the Different Study Groups

In the nasal fluid samples, median values tests of significance, convalescent IgA S1-RBD median reading is statistically more significant than IgG-NCP value of $p < 0.045$, this would encourage suggesting that IgA is the preferred test in the nasal fluid to tract the severity and serological immunity of infected individuals.

In case of vaccination a statistically non-significant difference $p < 0.424$ between IgA S1-RBD and IgG-NCP still a slight median value higher in case of IgA S1-RBD, suggesting that IgA is may be preferred over IgG in the nasal fluid, see (Table 4.14).

Table 4.14: comparison between the IgA and IgG between the different study groups in nasal fluid.

Study Group	Mann–Whitney <i>U</i> test	Sig.	IgG	IgA
Vaccinated	143.0000	0.424	1.52 COI for A ^o	1.84 COI for A ^o
Control	86.50 **	0.010	0.34 COI for A ^o	0.71 COI for A ^o
Convalescent	64.00 **	0.045	1.47 COI for A ^o	1.94 COI for A ^o

Discussion involves comparing Immunoglobulins in the nasal fluid of the different study groups:

Based on (Fröberg *et al.*, 2021) All things considered, our research demonstrates that an early and stronger nasal antibody response may be crucial in preventing illness by triggering early viral clearance and accelerating the cure of systemic symptoms. To confirm the function of nasal antibodies in clinical protection, further study is required. Nasal IgA and IgG antibodies are still detected nine months after infection and probably provide some protection from re-infection. Monitoring post-infection and post-vaccination nasal antibody levels may help us to spot early indications of the diminishing immunity against infection since mucosal antibodies are the first line of defense against viral infection. Finally, the study design and analytic approach described here might serve as a model for further research into COVID-19 and other viral disorders.

Our result suggests, that IgA is the preferred test in the nasal fluid to track the severity and serological immunity of infected patients, according to convalescent IgA S1-RBD mean readings that are statistically more significant than IgG-NCP values of $p = 0.045$ in nasal fluid samples. In the case of post vaccination, while being statistically insignificant ($p = 0.424$), there was a modest mean value advantage for IgA S1-RBD over IgG-NCP, indicating that IgA may be favored over IgG in the nasal fluid.

Nasal immunoglobulins in normal healthy individuals appears to be derived from pericellular effusion as well as mucosal secretions of the anterior serous glands, seromucous glands, and bowman glands within the nasal mucosa. As stated by (Kirkeby *et al.*, 2000), In a few instances, serum-type immunoglobulins—primarily serum IgG and serum IgA—contributed considerably to the local

immunoglobulin protection of the nasal mucosa of healthy individuals. Studies of rhinitis patients' nasal secretions have shown larger ratios of serum-type IgA compared to S-IgA and almost similar quantities of the IgG and IgA isotypes. This is likely due to an increase in the availability of IgG and monomeric serum IgA via inflammatory exudate, since these immunoglobulins, unlike S-IgA, diffuse passively into secretions.

However, it has also been shown that IgG and serum IgA account for significant percentages of immunoglobulins in nasal secretions of people without nasal irritation. The disparity between their data and ours might be the result of different quantitative techniques being used. Radial immunodiffusion was therefore used in a number of earlier research, which is likely to undervalue S-IgA in comparison to monomeric immunoglobulin forms. S-IgA was reported to make up a median of 57% (range, 39 to 77%) of the total IgA in nasal secretions of healthy children in one investigation employing ELISAs similar to ours, but the studies did not involve separation of serum-type IgA and S-IgA prior to quantification.

Establishing the fact that SARS-COV-2 vaccination would elicit a mucosal specific immunity, to SARS-COV-2 infection, in addition to systemic immunity, this would pave the way for an important understanding of how humanity would overcome this raging pandemic. The current study, indicates that COVID-19 vaccination can trigger mucosal immunity derived from the humoral immunity, and serological based investigations are a growing candidate, for a cost-effective and non-invasive tracker of vaccine elicited protective immune defense against the viral infection.

4.c- The Comparative Vaccine Efficacy versus Placebo Study

4.c.1- Vaccination Efficacy Parameters

The prospective study groups, was subdivided into three groups. The single vaccination group, two vaccination group, and the three-vaccination group.

The single vaccination group, subjects were taken from AlSalam vaccination ward upon first vaccination, were signed a patients information sheet and consent form detailing all study steps and procedures, this group were instructed to retake vaccination after 90 days to study the single dose efficacy as well as safety outcomes from vaccine administration.

The percentage COVID-19 case incidence in this group was 25% (5 out of 20 subjects), reflecting a roughly 75% protection from COVID-19 infection over a period of 90 days, (Table 4.15). As compared to retrospective group the percentage COVID-19 case incidence was 77% (27 out of 35 subject) over the retrospective follow up period of 90 days, reflecting a roughly 23% protection from COVID-19 infection over the entire 90 days from protection free exposure time.

The two-dose vaccination group, subjects were taken from Al Salam vaccination ward upon second vaccination dose, were signed a patients information sheet and consent form detailing all study steps and procedures, this group were instructed to either retake vaccination after 90 days or not, in order to study the two doses efficacy as well as safety outcomes from vaccine administration.

The percentage COVID-19 case incidence in this group was 7.7% (1 out of 13 subjects), reflecting a roughly 92.3% protection from COVID-19 infection over

a period of 90 days, (Table 4.15). As compared to retrospective group the percentage COVID-19 case incidence was 77% (27 out of 35 subject) over the retrospective follow up period of 90 days, reflecting a roughly 23% protection from COVID-19 infection over the entire 90 days from protection free exposure time.

The triple vaccination group, subjects were taken from Al Salam vaccination ward upon third vaccination, were signed a patients information sheet and consent form detailing all study steps and procedures, this group were instructed to report vaccination side effects for 90 days follow up period, to have a complete triple dose efficacy as well as safety outcomes from vaccine administration.

The percentage COVID-19 case incidence in this group was 0% (0 out of 7 subjects), reflecting a roughly 100% protection from COVID-19 infection over a period of 90 days, (Table 4.15). As compared to retrospective group the percentage COVID-19 case incidence was 77% (27 out of 35 subject) over the retrospective follow up period of 90 days, reflecting a roughly 23% protection from COVID-19 infection over the entire 90 days from protection free exposure time.

Table 4.15: Number and percentage of vaccinated versus placebo, COVID-19 infection percent after 3 months follow up.

Primary end point	BNT162b2		Percentage incidence of cases	Placebo*		Percentage incidence of cases	RRR Vaccine Efficacy**
	No. Of cases	Population		No. Of cases	Population		
COVID-19 occurrence 90 days after the first dose in participants without evidence of prior infection	5	20	25%	27	35	77%	69.33%
COVID-19 occurrence 90 days after the second dose in participants without evidence of prior infection	1	13	7.7%	27	35	77%	75%
COVID-19 occurrence 90 days after the third dose in participants without evidence of prior infection	0	7	0%	27	35	77%	77%

* All cases of placebo were drawn from retrospective follow up group.

** RRR of protection % is the reverse of incidence %, and calculation is taken on this basis.

Comparative parameter for vaccine efficacy is made utilizing the relative risk ratio, reflecting on the protection incidence from different number of vaccination doses compared to placebo. In the first dose vaccination group, the RRR was (69.33%) protection as compared to placebo group. This reflects a protective ratio for a single vaccination shot compared to placebo. If we consider the double

vaccination regime, we find that the RRR was (75%) still reflects some superiority over single vaccination dose, and comparatively high superior protection compared to placebo arm. If we take the final three doses vaccination group, the RRR is (77%) this adds on to the single and double doses groups protection strength and yet give the superior protection as compared to the placebo arm.

Cumulative protection percentage as a mean from all vaccination doses protective percentages was (89.1%) this number reflects the overall vaccination group protection percent following vaccination as compared to placebo, see (Figure 4.4). If we consider the RRR for this percentage number as compared to placebo, it would be (74.2%) for all vaccination doses groups, this gives a collective superiority of vaccination over placebo under all terms and conditions. According to other analyses, vaccine effectiveness across subgroups characterized by age, sex, race, ethnicity, obesity, and the presence of a concomitant ailment was largely consistent with that seen in the general population (Table 4.16, 4.17).

Table 4.16: population detailing three-month follow-up for vaccine effectiveness against COVID-19

BNT162b2							
Study population	Number	1st vaccine	% Case incidenc e	2nd vaccine	% Case incidenc e	3rd vaccine	% Case incidenc e
Total	40						
Age							
>15-50	22	2	5%	0	0%	0	0%
>50	8	1	2.5%	0	0%	0	0%
>60	6	2	5%	1	2.5%	0	0%
>75	4	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%
Gender							
Male	16	1	2.5%	1	2.5%	0	0%
Female	24	4	10%	0	0%	0	0%
Illness							
Hypertension	5	1	2.5%	0	0%	0	0%
Diabetes	9	3	7.5%	1	2.5%	0	0%
IHD*	6	1	2.5%	0	0%	0	0%
RDs*	3	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%

Table 4.17: population detailing three-month follow-up for COVID-19 incidence in placebo group.

Study population	Number	Placebo					
		30 days	% Case incidence	60 days	% Case incidence	90 days	% Case incidence
Total	35						
Age							
>15-50	17	5	14.3%	6	17.14%	2	5.7%
>50	5	2	5.7%	1	2.85%	1	2.85%
>60	8	0	0%	2	5.7%	3	8.6%
>75	5	0	0%	0	0%	5	14.3%
Gender							
Male	16	2	5.7%	5	14.3%	4	11.42%
Female	24	5	14.3%	4	11.42%	7	20%
Illness							
Hypertension	7	1	2.85%	2	5.7%	1	2.85%
Diabetes	14	4	11.42%	4	11.42%	7	20%
IHD*	11	2	5.7%	3	8.6%	2	5.7%
RDs*	3	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%

4.c.2- Vaccination Safety Parameters

Local Reactions

There were 40 people in the subset of reactogenicity. Compared to placebo receivers, BNT162b2 recipients often reported higher local reactions. Less than 3% of participants across all age categories reported severe discomfort, with mild-to-moderate pain at the injection site within 7 days of an injection being the most often reported local reaction among BNT162b2 recipients (Figure 4.5). Individuals over the age of 55 reported pain less frequently (64% after the first dosage and 47% after the second) than participants under the age of 55 (86% after the first dose and 79% after the second dose). Participants who reported redness or edema at the injection site were much less common. After the second dose, the percentage of participants reporting local reactions remained constant (Figure 4.5), and no participant reported a grade 4 local reaction. Local reactions typically ranged from mild to moderate in severity and subsided within 1 to 2 days.

Systemic Reactions

In the reactogenicity subgroup, younger vaccination receivers (16 to 55 years old) than older vaccine recipients (more than 55 years old) experienced systemic symptoms more often, and after dose 2, dose 3 than dose 1 (Figure 4.6). Although fatigue and headache were frequently reported by many placebo subjects (17% and 20%, respectively after the questionnaire, especially among younger subjects); and (14% and 11% among older subjects), they were the most frequently reported systemic events (47% and 61%, respectively, after the second dose, among younger vaccine recipients; 42% and 31%, among recipients who were older vaccine recipients). Slightly higher percent was reported for the third dose recipient (54% and 69%, respectively for younger subjects) and (51% and 37% for the older vaccine subjects). After the first dosage, there were a slight increase in fatigue and headache compared to what were reported in placebo subjects group following questionnaire, as (41% and 58% in younger subjects; and 39% and 27% in older subjects). There were no serious systemic events more often than 0.6%, except for a serious fatigue (4.1%) and serious headache (2.9%) after the second dose, and (4.7% and 3.2% respectively) after the third dose; severe systemic effects were only recorded in fewer than 1.8% of vaccination users.

After the second dosage, 14% of younger and 9.5% of older vaccination recipients reported having a fever (temperature, 38°C). Third dose subjects had 13% and 11% respectively in such fever level. First dose subjects had a slight fever reaction in compare, as (4% in younger and 3% in older subjects), over all placebo subjects from questionnaire reported negligible fever as (2% in young and 1% in elderly).

Two members of the vaccination group noted a fever more than 40.0°C. Younger vaccine recipients had higher rates of antipyretic or pain medication use (24% after dose 1, 39% after dose 2, and 43% after dose 3) than older vaccine recipients (18%

after dose 1, 31% after dose 2, and 39% after dose 3), while placebo subjects, regardless of age or dose, had lower rates of medication use (12–15%) than vaccine recipients, according to questionnaire. After immunization, systemic symptoms including fever and chills were sometimes seen for the first one to two days before going away.

Serious side effects

All 75 subjects who were recruited are given adverse event analyses, with varying levels of follow-up after dosage 1 (Table 4.15). BNT162b2 patients (23% vs. 16%, respectively) reported any adverse event or a connected adverse event (26% vs. 6%). Transient reactogenicity events, which were more often reported as adverse events by vaccination recipients than by placebo receivers, are mostly reflected in this distribution. (2.5%) of vaccination recipients with lymphadenopathy. Rarely did either group's members have severe adverse events, significant adverse events, or adverse events that required them to withdraw from the experiment. Among BNT162b2 recipients, there were two linked significant adverse events (shoulder injury related to vaccine administration, right axillary lymphadenopathy, paroxysmal ventricular arrhythmia, and right leg paresthesia). One of the placebo patients passed away (from respiratory distress), while none of the BNT162b2 recipients did, the researchers did not believe that any fatalities were caused by the

vaccination or a placebo. There was one fatality linked to COVID-19.

Figure 4.4: Efficacy of BNT162b2 against COVID-19 after three cumulative doses. Shown is the cumulative incidence of COVID-19 after the first dose (modified intention-to-treat population). Each symbol represents COVID-19 cases starting on a given day.

Figure 4.5: Rates of reported Local reactions, by Age Group. 7 Days BNT162b2 Injection. **a.** subjects above 55 years of age. **b.** subjects below 55 years of age.

Figure 4.6: Rates of reported systemic reactions, by Age Group, 7 Days BNT162b2 Injection

Discussion regarding the comparative vaccine efficacy versus placebo study

The effectiveness of BNT162b2 against COVID-19 was determined to be 89.1% after three doses (30 µg each dosage), given 21 days apart. Both of the vaccine's key efficacy end goals were satisfied. These outcomes far beyond the minimal FDA authorization requirements while meeting our predetermined success criteria (Emergency Use Authorization for Vaccines Explained, 2020).

The point estimates of efficacy for subgroups based on age, sex, medication history, body mass index, or the presence of an underlying condition associated with a high risk of COVID-19 complications are also high, despite the fact that the study was not powered to conclusively assess efficacy by subgroup. More than 10 COVID-19 instances in any of the examined subgroups may provide insight into the subgroups' relationships to COVID-19 susceptibility.

By 12 days after the first dose, or 7 days after the estimated median viral incubation period of 5 days, the cumulative incidence of COVID-19 cases over time among retrospective placebo and vaccine recipients starts to diverge, (Cortés Martínez *et al.*, 2022), indicating the early onset of a partially protective effect of immunization. The effectiveness of a single-dose regimen was not intended to be evaluated in this research. Nevertheless, the observed vaccine efficacy against COVID-19 infection was 75% between the first and second doses, and it was 93.3% in the first 7 days following dose 2, reaching full efficacy against disease with onset at least 7 days after dose 2, and 100% in the first 7 days following dose 3. This indicates a sharp efficacy against COVID-19 infection. Only 5 of the 32 severe COVID-19 cases that were seen after the first dosage occurred in the group that received the vaccination. This result is in line with the strong comparative effectiveness overall versus all COVID-19 instances. The severe case split allays many of the theoretical worries about vaccine-mediated disease enhancement by

providing early evidence of vaccine-mediated protection against serious illness, (Li *et al.*, 2022).

BNT162b2's positive safety profile, which was discovered during phase 1 testing, (Chen *et al.*, 2022, Guerrero *et al.*, 2021), was verified throughout the phase 2 and phase 3 of the study. Similar to phase 1, reactogenicity was often low or moderate, and older persons had fewer and milder responses than younger adults. Local reactogenicity was equal after the three doses, while systemic reactogenicity was more frequent and severe after the second dosage than after the first dose. Nearly 44% of BNT162b2 users had severe fatigue, which is higher than that observed in recipients of some vaccinations suggested for senior citizens, (Li *et al.*, 2021). Additionally, this incidence of extreme fatigue is less frequent than that seen in older persons who received another viral vaccination that has been licensed for use, (*SHINGRIX*, 2021).

Overall, reactogenicity occurrences were brief and ended a few days after they began. Lymphadenopathy, which typically went away after 10 days, was probably brought on by a strong immunological reaction to the vaccination. In the vaccination and retrospective placebo groups, the rate of major adverse events was comparable (0.5% and 0.35%, respectively).

There are a number of restrictions on this experiment and its early findings. The study has a greater than 45% probability of detecting at least one adverse event, if the true incidence is 0.01%, with an average of 40 participants per group in the subset of participants with a median follow-up time of three months after the first dose, but it is not large enough to reliably detect less common adverse events. This report covers the study participants' three-month follow-up after the first vaccination dosage.

Therefore, it is yet unknown if side effects would manifest more than 3 to 4.5 months following the third dosage and how long protection will last. These findings do not address whether immunization prevents asymptomatic infection; a serologic end point (SARS-CoV-2 N-binding antibody) that may identify an infection history regardless of whether symptoms were present will be presented later, (Milani *et al.*, 2020). Furthermore, at the time of this publication, it was not possible to establish a correlation of protection due to the high vaccination efficiency and the limited number of vaccine breakthrough cases. The prevention of COVID-19 in other groups, including as younger adolescents, children, and pregnant women, is not included in this paper.

When the vaccine is prepared for use, it may be kept for up to 5 days in a conventional refrigerator, but shipment and extended storage need very low temperatures, (Storage and Handling of Pfizer-BioNTech COVID-19 Vaccines | CDC, 2022). The continuing stability investigations and formulation improvement, which may also be included in forthcoming reports, may reduce the need for the present cold storage requirement.

The relevance of the results in this research goes beyond the efficacy of the vaccine candidate. The results show that vaccination can prevent COVID-19 (UpToDate, n.d.). On January 10, 2020, the SARS-CoV-2 genomic sequence was made public by the Chinese Center for Disease Control and Prevention and distributed across the world under the GISAID (Global Project on Sharing All Influenza Data) initiative (China Releases Genetic Data on New Coronavirus, Now Deadly, 2020).

This marked the beginning of the creation of BNT162b2. Less than 11 months later, this thorough evaluation of safety and effectiveness shows how effective RNA-based vaccines may be in preventing pandemics and other infectious

disease outbreaks (Machado *et al.*, 2021). These vaccines can be developed using just the viral genetic sequence information.

The BNT162b2 vaccination is authorized in the context of the present trial and will keep helping, together with other public health measures, to lessen the tragic loss of health, life, and economic and social well-being that has occurred as a consequence of the worldwide spread of COVID-19.

Chapter Five

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study comes with the following conclusion:

- 1: Follow up of mucosal humoral immune response, at the site of viral entry would be a successful method to investigate the extent of vaccine-induced immunity,
- 2: Track kinetics of antibody response decay, provide a novel port of investigation to add a more effective and less invasive technique in SARS-COV-2 antibody detection,
- 3: Two doses of mRNA BNT162b2 COVID-19 vaccine (Comirnaty), would trigger a robust protective immune response, and secondary prevention of COVID-19 infection among vaccinated members.

From this stand point, future study directed toward a decision-making process, based on mucosal antibody detection and follow up, in term of timing of booster vaccination doses and the extent of need and duration of facial mask protection.

To summarize our study, in a brief conclusion, the presented data reflects that the mRNA BNT162b2 COVID-19 vaccine (Comirnaty), triggers a mucosal immunity of highly antigen specific characteristic. A remarkably high concentrations of secretory IgA monoclonal antibodies selective against the S1 protein, could be isolated in the nasal fluid and saliva from the subjects who have

been vaccinated at least the first dose vaccination. Such humoral mucosal immunity is triggered in vaccinated as well as subjects recovered or recovering from COVID-19 natural infection. Since to date no systematic standardized kits or assay for salivary as well as nasal fluid investigations of immunoglobulin concentration, in this study we proposed the same kits for humoral antibody detection to be used in salivary and nasal secretion investigation of IgA and IgG, to reflect a solid and consistent data derived from SARS-CoV-2 S1 and RBD proteins of the virus. the mRNA BNT162b2 COVID-19 vaccine (Comirnaty), also triggered a robust immunity in the humoral circulation suggestive of protective role of vaccine against future outbreaks in term of decreasing the intensity and the severity of symptoms of COVID-19 infection and only a mild flu like symptoms would be anticipated upon future immune escape of the virus. Regarding oral link to vaccination, we can conclude that systemic vaccination can trigger systemic humoral immunity that extend to the nasal cavity mucosal surface via capillary leakage and interstitial perfusion to illicit a strong local immunity against future attacks derived already from the humoral immunity. Same is with salivary IgG derived from GCF leakage as well as local parotid gland plasma cells that help to release enough monoclonal antibodies to the saliva to act as a shielding barrier from future attacks all derived from vaccine induced humoral immunity.

Recommendations:

- 1- future study directed toward a decision-making process, based on mucosal antibody detection and follow up, in term of timing of booster vaccination doses and the extent of need and duration of facial mask protection.
- 2- Investigating the local mucosal use of RAS system modulators as a potential preventive agent for inhibiting SARS CoV 2 infection in animal model.

- 3- Il-6 modulators use and investigation of mucosal immunity inhibition and extent of severity of COVID-19 as reflected by mucosal markers.
- 4- Effect of oral condition such as gingival inflammation, on the extent and severity of side effects after COVID-19 vaccination.
- 5- Retrospective investigation about the association between il-6 triggering infectious disease, and the extent and severity of cytokine storm in COVID-19 infection.
- 6- Study possible alterations in the oral microbiome of individuals with a healthy oral environment following COVID-19 vaccination
- 7- Utilizing salivary antibody assay to understand what does “fully vaccinated” against COVID-19 actually mean.
- 8- Investigate the vaccine effectiveness and the possibility of vaccine failure using salivary and nasal fluid investigation tests.
- 9- Can salivary testing of commensal viral community of oral cavity shed light on future pandemic of concern, as being considered a vital port of entry of many frequent pandemic and epidemic outbreaks.
- 10- IgM salivary concentration still not well understood to the moment, for being a marker of early infection, still a subject of interest in the future studies.

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Appendix I – patient Consent form.

CONSENT TO PARTICIPATE IN RESEARCH

Living humans Study

You are invited to participate in a research study conducted by Ghaith AlTaja, who is a master student from the college of Dentistry at Mosul University. Mr. Ghaith is conducting this study for his master dissertation. Dr. Ghada A. Younis is his faculty supervisor for this project. This study is self-funded.

Your participation in this study is entirely voluntary. You should read the information below and ask questions about anything you do not understand, before deciding whether or not to participate. You are being asked to participate in this study because you are a COVID-19 patient.

• PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of this study is to see how well the Serum based kit would give us a result using saliva samples. We hope to use what we learn from the study to make changes to the diagnostic approach of COVID-19, so it will help people who are at risk to avoid getting the disease by rapid and effective diagnosis.

• PROCEDURES

If you volunteer to participate in this study, we will ask you to do the following:

1. Give a blood sample of 5 ml via phlebotomy procedure.
2. Give a saliva sample of 3 ml via spitting into a plastic bottle

• POTENTIAL RISKS AND DISCOMFORTS

We expect that any risks, discomforts, or inconveniences will be minor and we believe that they are not likely to happen. If discomforts become a problem, you may discontinue your participation.

• POTENTIAL BENEFITS TO SUBJECTS AND/OR TO SOCIETY

It is not likely that you will benefit directly from participation in this study, but the research should help us learn how to improve services for people with physical disabilities who have recently been discharged from the hospital for physical or occupational therapy and other assistance before moving to their own home.

This study does not include procedures that will improve your physical disability or general health.

• COMPENSATION FOR PARTICIPATION

You will not receive any payment or other compensation for participation in this study. There is also no cost to you for participation.

• CONFIDENTIALITY

Any information that is obtained in connection with this study and that can be identified with you will remain confidential and will be disclosed only with your permission or as required by law. Confidentiality will be maintained by means of a code number to let Mr. Ghaith and Dr. Ghada know who you are. We will not use your name in any of the information we get from this study or in any of the research reports. When the study is finished, we will destroy the list that shows which code number goes with your name.

Information that can identify you individually will not be released to anyone outside the study. Mr. Ghaith will, however, use the information collected in her dissertation and other publications. We also may use any information that we get from this study in any way we think is best for publication or education. Any information we use for publication will not identify you individually.

In case of an emergency, injury, or illness that occurs during this study, I hereby authorize the release of any and all health information to allow for medical care and treatment of my condition.

• PARTICIPATION AND WITHDRAWAL

You can choose whether or not to be in this study. If you volunteer to be in this study, you may withdraw at any time without consequences of any kind. You may also refuse to answer any questions you do not want to answer. There is no penalty if you withdraw from the study and you will not lose any benefits to which you are otherwise entitled. The investigator may withdraw you from this research if your physician tells us that continued participation may injure your health.

• IDENTIFICATION OF INVESTIGATORS

If you have any questions or concerns about the research, please feel free to contact

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I understand the procedures described above. My questions have been answered to my satisfaction, and I agree to participate in this study. I have been given a copy of this form.

Printed Name of Subject

Signature of Subject

Date

Signature of Witness

Date

Appendix II - patient information sheet to take the full data.

Patient Medical Information Sheet

Name _____ Birth Date _____ Age _____

Reason for Visit _____ Date _____

Allergies to Medications _____

Current Medications _____

Name and dose _____

Over the counter meds _____

Other doctors you currently see _____

Your Past Medical History (all information is kept strictly confidential)

Surgeries (dates) _____

Hospitalizations _____

Women **First day of last period** _____ **Birth control** _____

	Last Pap smear _____	Number of pregnancies _____	number of children _____
	Last Mammogram _____	Family history of breast cancer _____	
Men	last prostate exam _____	Family history of Prostate cancer _____	

Blood transfusion Y N ... IV drug use Y N r N

Needle sticks Y N work with body fluids Y N tattoos and body piercing Y N sex with known AIDS or Hepatitis B or C Y N

HM & Hepatitis risks Diabetes Cancer Hepatitis	(Immunizations: check each disease and date of last COVID-19 Pneumonia Tetanus (every 10 years) Do you have a history of the following: High blood pressure High Cholesterol Epilepsy/seizures Pneumonia/Asthma Migraine headaches Thyroid (high/low)	Hepatitis B Influenza	- Hepatitis A MMR Heart disease/attack Sinus infections Depression
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COVID-19 Review Family history of COVID-19 date of first infection

date of reinfection Date of reinfection after vaccination

Detail: _____

Smoking Y N packs per Day Tried to quit? Y N

Alcohol use Y N drinks per week What do you drink? _____

Drug use Y N _____ **Diet** Food allergies _____

FAMILY Medical History

Cancer	Diabetes	Heart disease	high blood pressure
Depression	Stroke	High Cholesterol	Asthma Emphysema

Details _____

Signature _____ Physician review _____

Appendix III – Manufacturer specification of the operation kit and COI values.

EUROIMMUN
a PerkinElmer company

Medizinische
Labordiagnostika
AG

Anti-SARS-CoV-2 NCP ELISA (IgG)

- Sensitive detection of IgG against SARS-CoV-2 using the nucleocapsid protein
- Antigen with the strongest immune dominance in the coronavirus family
- Optimised specificity of the ELISA due to the use of a modified nucleocapsid protein (NCP) that only contains diagnostically relevant epitopes
- Validated for serum, plasma and dried capillary blood as the sample material; fully automatable

Technical data

Antigen	Modified nucleocapsid protein (NCP)
Calibration	Semiquantitative; calculation of a ratio from the extinction of the sample and that of the calibrator
Result interpretation	EUROIMMUN recommends interpreting results as follows: Ratio < 0.8: negative Ratio ≥ 0.8 to < 1.1: borderline Ratio ≥ 1.1: positive
Sample dilution	Serum or plasma, 1:101 in sample buffer, or 4.76 mm punched out membrane piece with dried capillary blood in 250 µl sample buffer
Reagents	Ready for use, with the exception of the wash buffer (10x); colour-coded solutions, in most cases exchangeable with those in other EUROIMMUN ELISA kits
Test procedure	60 min (37°C) / 30 min (RT) / 15 min (RT) (sample/conjugate/substrate incubations), fully automatable
Measurement	450 nm, reference wavelength between 620 nm and 650 nm
Test kit format	96 break-off wells; kit includes all necessary reagents
Stability	12 months
Order number	EI 2606-9601-2 G; EI 2606-9620-2 G (designed especially for processing on the EUROLabWorkstation ELISA)

الطريقة:

أجرينا بحثنا للكشف عن الأجسام المضادة وحيدة النسيلة المصلية لفيروس سارز-كوف-2 من نوع الغلوبولين المناعي ج -ضد قفيصة البروتين النووي و ايضا الغلوبولين المناعي أ - ضد نطاق الارتباط بالمستلم ، في عينة من ثلاث مجموعات عشوائية من المرضى (إجمالي 55 شخصا، تم تقسيمهم عشوائياً إلى 20 شخصاً غير مصابين سابقاً ، 20 شخصاً تم تطعيمهم بالكامل من ردهة التطعيم بمستشفى السلام التعليمي في الموصل عند تلقي جرعات اللقاح ، و 15 مريضاً شُفيوا حديثاً من عدوى سارز-كوف-2 من مستشفى الشفاء للحجر الصحي بعد واثناء تعافيتهم من عدوى كوفيد-19 والاستعداد للخروج) في ثلاث عينات سوائل مصل ولعاب وسوائل أنف ، بواقع ثلاث عينات لكل مشارك ، لجعل إجمالي 165 عينة ليتم اختبارها ، باستخدام عدة فحص مناعية تجارية من نوع (فحص إليزا المخصص للكشف عن الغلوبولين المناعي أ - ضد نطاق الارتباط بالمستلم و فحص إليزا المخصص للكشف عن الغلوبولين المناعي ج - ضد قفيصة البروتين النووي).

هذه الدراسة صممت لتقييم مستويات الغلوبولين المناعي في كل عينة من مختلف الحالات الصحية والمناطق التشريحية لإعطاء الفرق الإحصائي والاستنتاج الصحيح فيما يتعلق بهذه الدراسة. تم إجراء التحليل الإحصائي باستخدام الإصدار 24 من برنامج (الحزمة الاحصائية للعلوم المناعية) ، بالإضافة إلى إصدار (16.0.15028) اكسل مايكروسوفت، وتم إجراء معادلات الاختبار عبر اختبار مان ويتني يو، وكذلك اختبار كروسكال واليس اج ، لتقييم التوزيع غير الغاوسي بين مجموعات الدراسة ، لكل نتيجة من النتائج ، تم اعتبار قيمة $P < 0.05$ ذات دلالة إحصائية.

نتائج:

أظهر عملنا أن جرعتين من لقاح الحمض النووي الريبوزي المسمى تجارياً بـ "كوميرناتي بي ان تي 162 بي2 المصنع من قبل شركة فايزر/بايونتك" ، نيويورك ، نيويورك ، الولايات المتحدة الأمريكية) ، أثار تكوين مقاومة قوية ضد سارز-كوف-2 في الأنف واللحاج من نوع الغلوبولين المناعي من نوع اي و الغلوبولين المناعي من نوع جي وحيدة النسيلة (بالمقارنة مع مجموعة المقايسة الذي كانت نتائجها لمتوسط مستوى السيروم الغلوبولين المناعي من نوع جي - ضد قفيصة البروتين النووي كان 0.625 القيمة الحدية، مقارنة بالأشخاص الملقحين ارتفاع متوسط تركيز اللعاب لمتوسط مستوى السيروم الغلوبولين المناعي لنفس النوع لقيم 1.69 القيمة الحدية، مع قيمة $p < 0.0001$ ، للدلالة على احصائية المقارنة. ينطبق الأمر نفسه على متوسط التركيز اللعابي لسيروم الغلوبولين المناعي من نوع اي ضد نطاق الارتباط بالمستلم، للأشخاص الذين تم تلقيحهم في بقيمة 2.41 القيمة الحدية ، مقارنة بقيم مجموعة المقايسة 0.67 القيمة الحدية ، مع قيمة $p < 0.0001$) ، بالمقارنة بقيم مجموعة المقايسة 0.34 القيمة الحدية ، نتج عن الأشخاص الذين تم تلقيحهم تركيز سائل أنفي السيروم الغلوبولين المناعي من نوع جي - ضد قفيصة البروتين النووي بمتوسط 1.52 القيمة الحدية ، مع قيمة $p < 0.0001$. وينطبق نفس الشيء على متوسط تركيز الأنف من الغلوبولين المناعي من نوع اي ضد نطاق الارتباط بالمستلم بقيمة 1.84 القيمة الحدية ، مقارنة بقيم التحكم الوسيطة 0.71 القيمة الحدية. حققتان بينهما 25 يوماً من اللقاح ظهر أنهما يطلقان عياراً أقوى من المناعة الوقائية مقارنةً بالحقنة المبكرة الفردية ، إلا أنه لا يزال أقل قوة مقارنةً بالعيار المقاس للأشخاص الذين تم شفائهم من عدوى كوفيد-19. مع الأخذ في الاعتبار أنه كان هناك نقص في الاختبارات والعدد الفحصية المعتمدة على

إليزا الموثوق بها مع مجموعة مصممة خصيصاً لهذا الغرض ، مع التركيز على إفرازات الأنف واللعاب ، أثبتت الدراسة الحالية أن بياناتنا السابقة للتحقيق ودراستنا التحقيقية كانت متطابقة النتائج . تشير نتائج هذه الدراسة إلى أنه يمكن تحفيز الجسم المضاد أحادي النسيلة الأنفي واللعابي الوقائي الخاص بالمستضد لفيروس كوفيد-19 ، باتباع نظام التطعيم المناسب بلقاح كوفيد-19 من نوع الحمض النووي الريبوزي ، لذلك يمهد هذا الطريق لاستخدام الكشف عن الأجسام المضادة الوقائية المخاطية ، كخيار بديل مناسب. طريقة أقل تأثيراً على المريض مقارنةً بفحوصات المصل ، باستخدام مجموعات للكشف عن الحماية ضد عدوى سارز-كوف-2، التي يسببها اللقاح. اوضحت نتائج اختبار الأشخاص الملقحين متوسط تكوين الاجسام المضادة النسيلة بشكل أفضل من نوع الغلوبولين المناعي من نوع اي في اللعاب مقارنة بـ الغلوبولين المناعي من نوع جي ، واثت القيم المتوسطة الأعلى لـ الغلوبولين المناعي من نوع اي مقابل الغلوبولين المناعي من نوع جي بحيث 2.41 القيمة الحديدية و 1.69 القيمة الحديدية على التوالي بقيمة $p < 0.008$. في حالة مماثلة ، فإن الغلوبولين المناعي من نوع اي هو أفضل اختبار للأشخاص الذين عبروا فترة النقاهة من حيث فحوصات عينات السائل الأنفي ، حيث أن القيمة المتوسطة أعلى نسبياً من القيمة المتوسطة لـ الغلوبولين المناعي من نوع جي بـ 1.94 القيمة الحديدية و 1.47 القيمة الحديدية على التوالي ، مع قيمة $p < 0.045$.

وزارة التعليم العالي والبحث العلمي

جامعة الموصل

كلية طب الأسنان

التحري عن الكلوبولينات المناعية ضد فايروس سارس-كوف-2 كالغلوبولين المناعي من النوع جي والغلوبولين المناعي من نوع اي في عينات اللعاب والمصل والسائل الانفي في المرضى باستخدام اختبار المقايسة المناعية الإنزيمية (إليزا)

رسالة مقدمة

الى جامعة الموصل - كلية طب الأسنان

من قبل

غيث ربيع محمد صالح الطائي

كجزء من متطلبات لنيل شهادة الماجستير في الأحياء المجهرية الفموية

بإشراف

الأستاذ المساعد الدكتورة غادة يونس عبدالرحمن

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